

Ollscoil na hÉireann, Corcaigh
National University of Ireland, Cork

**The Challenge of Sustainability for Digital Projects in the Humanities in
Ireland. A Case Study of the Munster Women Writers Project.**

Thesis presented by

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for the degree of

Master of Arts

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2022

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Declaration

This is to certify that the work I am submitting is my own and has not been submitted for another degree, either at University College Cork or elsewhere. All external references and sources are clearly acknowledged and identified within the contents. I have read and understood the regulations of University College Cork concerning plagiarism and intellectual property.

Abstract

This dissertation examines the challenges of sustainability for digital projects in the Humanities in Ireland. It takes a broad view of the term ‘digital humanities’ as one encompassing any digital outputs from Humanities scholars. In particular it focuses on the sustainability issues in the context of the Irish landscape and the *munsterwomen.ie* website, a resource no longer in the digital domain.

It addresses the issue of sustainability in two ways. Firstly, at a theoretical level it uses a literature review to identify the key challenges in the field as access, availability, longevity, funding and lack of policy and vision. It sees these issues as infrastructural challenges that require: a shift by the Academy in the manner in which it rewards and values digital output; the development of advocacy alliances and strong peer support networks; the development of a national strategy for digital humanities output and a central digital repository to support the needs of Humanities scholars in the era of Open Access research. It concludes that digital Humanities research, the output of publicly funded Irish scholarship, should be presented to the wider community via a national repository, accessible to all.

The dissertation also addresses the challenge of sustainability practically by taking as a case study the Munster Women Writers project and creating a proof-of-concept digital resource to return that project’s website to the digital realm after an absence of almost a decade. Noting a gap in the literature of practical examples for the recovery of similar ‘lost’ digital projects it uses the Omeka CMS to create a new web resource, providing a detailed overview of the process for others to follow. It focusses on using tools and technologies that have low barriers to access for Humanities scholars, whether that be technical expertise, time or financial resources. Open Access and adherence to FAIR principles, key tenets of the current research funding landscape, are considered of paramount importance throughout the process. A key output of the dissertation is a guide for others undertaking similar projects which synthesises the learnings from both the literature review and the creation of the digital artefact.

Keywords: Sustainability, Digital Humanities, Humanities, Technology, Omeka, Digital Archives, Metadata, Open Access

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisor Dr Orla Murphy for the support and advice she provided throughout the process of writing this dissertation. Her passion for, and dedication to, digital sustainability in the Humanities provided me with a stimulating environment in which to explore this often-overlooked topic.

I would like to thank Dr Tina O'Toole (University of Limerick) for the inspiration for this case study, both as the scholar on whose work the Munster Women Writers project website was based, and as the friend who suggested I was well-positioned to bring the data back to the digital realm.

I would like to thank Sinead Keogh (University of Limerick) who offered advice in the early stages of the project; Dr Michael Kurzmeier (University College Cork) who provided me with insight into web archiving challenges in Ireland; and Roberto Sabatino (HEAnet) who invited me to attend the RESIN update event.

I would like to thank June and Debora, my fellow MA students whose humour carried me through the long summer of writing. Ruth who fortified me with morning walks. And Mollie and Ciara who fortified me with coffee and cakes.

Finally I would like to thank Liz Powell, for her eagle-eyed editing and proof-reading, unwavering support and pep talks, and her adept Minna management.

This dissertation is dedicated to all of those who create and maintain digital archives whether in a personal or professional capacity, and in particular Jonathan Neville a volunteer on the original *munsterwomen.ie* website who had the foresight to create a zip archive of all the digital outputs of the project 'just in case'.

Digital Manifest

This Digital Manifest has been included to direct readers to the digital resources associated with this dissertation, adhering to a template proposed by Shirazi and Zweibel in *Documenting Digital Projects* (2020).

1. Digital Artefacts

- I. Link to live version of Munster Women Writers proof-of-concept website: <http://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/>
- II. An archived version of the Munster Women Writers proof-of-concept website can also be viewed on the Internet Archive at the following location: <https://web.archive.org/web/20220805115257/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/>
- III. Link to Mindmeister mind map ‘Digital Landscape of the Humanities in Ireland, August 2022’: <https://mm.tt/map/2345445780?t=AWrTwhN1ts>
- IV. Link to Mindmeister mind map ‘OpenAccess and Third Level Institutions in Ireland, August 2022’: <https://mm.tt/map/2348879434?t=7XGTq7e3VW>

2. Dissertation

- I. This PDF document.
- II. Archived version at: <https://github.com/joanmurphy/MWW/>

3. WARC Files

- I. Munster Women Writers proof-of-concept website
Archived version at: https://github.com/joanmurphy/MWW/blob/main/MWW_Joanofarchives_2022.warc
- II. MindMeister Maps
Archived version at: <https://github.com/joanmurphy/MWW/blob/main/MindMeisterPages.warc>

4. Supporting material

- I. All documents associated with this dissertation are available in the following GitHub repository. The repository is private at time of submission (August, 2022) please contact <joan.murphy@gmail.com> for access: <https://github.com/joanmurphy/MWW>
- II. Munster Women Writers original dataset as received from Jonathan Neville
<https://github.com/joanmurphy/MWW/blob/main/munsterwomen.com.rar>
- III. Munster Women Writers Data Dictionary
https://github.com/joanmurphy/MWW/blob/main/MWW_DataDictionary.docx
- IV. Munster Women Writers Project explanatory documents
<https://github.com/joanmurphy/MWW/blob/main/README.md>

Glossary of Terms

DOI	Digital Object Identifier. A unique code that can be assigned to any digital object. Used primarily as a unique identifier in online repositories.
FAIR	An acronym from ‘Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable’, a set of agreed principles applicable to research data
GLAM	An acronym from ‘Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums’, cultural institutions engaged with making knowledge accessible
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HEA	Higher Education Authority. The statutory policy-advisory body for higher education in Ireland
HEAnet	Ireland’s National Education and Research Network which delivers internet connectivity and ICT shared services to Irish education sector
Metadata	Often described as ‘data about data’ - examples for a book might include the title, the date and place of publication and the author
Open Access	A publishing model making research available at no cost to end-users
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting. A protocol allowing for the automatic collection of repository metadata by aggregators.
Open Data	Openly accessible, editable and shareable data
Open Source	Software with source code that anyone can inspect, modify, or enhance
WARC	An archival file format for websites, which can contain multiple resource types (CSS, HTML, audio, video etc.) in addition to archival metadata

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1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The chapter will begin by proposing the research problem as the sustainability challenge that currently exists for digital projects in the Humanities in Ireland. It will consider the intellectual challenge of returning the *munsterwomen.ie* resource, a previously lost project, back to the digital domain. The chapter will go on to set out two research objectives and propose six questions to be considered in order to satisfactorily address the objectives. This will be followed by a discussion of the research design and resources to be used, and the scope and limitations of the research will be outlined. The chapter will conclude with an overview of the organisation of the dissertation.

1.2 Research Problem

The research problem that this dissertation will address is the challenge of sustainability for digital projects in the Humanities in Ireland.

Davis (2019) finds that only 64% of 48 projects with an online component presented at DH2005 remain accessible. And an analysis by Estill (2019) of two major digital bibliographies from the early 2000s Evan's 'Internet Resources for Teaching Early Modern Women Writers' (2002) and Ziegler's 'Women Writers Online: An Evaluation and Annotated Bibliography of Web Resources' (2001) shows just 35% of the listed resources to be still online. Su and Zhang (2022) present a comprehensive survey of the research output and intellectual structures of Digital Humanities in a longitudinal analysis of DH research from 2005-2020. The focus of their study is the broad concept of the digital humanities rather than the more computational domain, which they identify as Humanities Computing.

Using bibliometric methods and network analysis they visualise results of their extensive review of research in the field identifying four distinct clusters of research (Fig. 1, below).

Figure 1 - Major research topics from author keywords. (Source: Su and Zhang 2022, p.683)

Their analysis identifies 4,655 keywords from c. 2000 articles and provides a list of the 30 keywords which occur most frequently. In Cluster 3, ‘Collaboration and interdisciplinarity’ (coloured yellow on their diagram above) keywords that are aspects of sustainability do appear and are highlighted below (Fig. 2) but the lack of the term ‘Sustainability’ itself is striking, and the authors themselves note it is only in recent years that ‘infrastructures emerge as [an] important theme’ (Su and Zhang, 2022, p.691).

<i>Sustainability topics highlighted by author</i>		
Cluster 3	Project, people, and infrastructure	project (479); challenge (249) ; scholar (232); resource (213); community (199); researcher (198); university (183); case study (177); role (176); library (168); collaboration (141); access (133) ; creation (133); scholarship (124); platform (123) ; institution (105); infrastructure (104) ; service (99); digital humanities project (91); communication (80); center (77); research project (75); librarian (73); management (73); cultural heritage (62); social science (62); organization (60); team (60); design methodology approach (59); museum (57); repository (51); digital library (47); computer science (42); humanities scholar (41); workshop (40); faculty (38); digital humanities research (37); digital scholarship (37); publishing (35); digital humanist (34); humanist (34); digital archive (33); digital resource (33); digital project (31); digital collection (27); open access (25) ; academic library (24); research process (23); archivist (21); DH project (21); digital humanities scholar (21); practical implication (19); best practice (18) ; digital humanities scholarship (18); digital humanities community (15)

Figure 2 - Research topics and themes. (Source: Su and Zhang, 2022, Table 2, p.681)

The absence of ‘sustainability’ as a discrete topic in the literature suggests a gap in the research currently being undertaken in the field. It is this lack of visibility of the challenges posed by sustainability issues for digital projects in the Humanities, specifically within an Irish context, that this paper seeks to address.

1.3 Intellectual Challenge

The Munster Women Writers (MWW) project was a literature project with a significant digital element, one of the first such projects to be undertaken in Ireland. It created a unique resource, available as a searchable online database of biographical and bibliographic information, making visible Munster women in literary culture. While the data were gathered in the form of a printed volume ‘Dictionary of Munster Women Writers, 1800-2000’ it was only available as an online resource for six years and has been digitally inaccessible since 2013.

The intellectual challenge is to (re)create this digital resource being mindful of the original project goal ‘to make more information on these writers available for future literary historians, feminist critics, and social historians to develop knowledge and understanding of this material’ (O’Toole, 2005). The methodology I propose seeks to combine Restoration and Repurposing (Antonini *et al.*, 2020): Restoration to the digital realm will focus on (re)formatting and (re)structuring of the data; while Repurposing will facilitate knowledge production by presenting and disseminating the

information. A further intellectual challenge will be to employ tools that adhere to FAIR Principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016) and Open Access guidelines, in line with meeting sustainability challenges.

1.4 Research Objectives

The research problem that this dissertation will address is the challenge of sustainability for digital projects in the Humanities in Ireland. This will be accomplished by meeting two objectives:

1. Identify challenges for sustainability of Irish digital Humanities projects
2. Offer a practical approach to meet sustainability challenges

It is proposed to do this by considering the following questions:

1. *What constitutes a digital Humanities project?* This will consider the issues arising in the Humanities field as technology is employed to enable research and enhance knowledge production.
2. *What are the key concepts and issues relating to sustainability in digital projects in the Humanities?* This will give the reader a grounding in the concepts and issues relating to sustainability.
3. *How did contemporaneous projects achieve sustainability?* This will examine two similar projects.
4. *What efforts are being made for similar 'lost' digital endeavours?* This will establish current thoughts on best practice in the recovery of legacy projects.
5. *What are the sustainability challenges in an Irish context?* This will interrogate some key sustainability challenges in the Irish landscape.
6. *What practical steps can be taken to address the sustainability challenge?* This will provide a concrete example of how digital sustainability can be achieved.

The first five questions will be addressed by way of a Literature Review. The final question will be addressed by the creation of a digital artefact which will provide a practical example of how digital sustainability can be achieved using low-cost Open Source tools and techniques to make

available a previously ‘lost’ digital resource. Taking as a case study the Munster Women Writers website *munsterwomen.ie*, it will offer one possible solution to the sustainability challenge, proposing processes, workflows and standards and using tools and techniques accessible to most in 2022.

1.5 Research Design

This dissertation will take the form of a case study, which will allow for the acquisition of practical context-specific information about the sustainability challenges for legacy digital humanities projects. This process will enable me to consider all of the challenges associated with restoring a legacy dataset to the digital domain, within clearly defined sustainability parameters. By using a subset of data from the MWW project I will create a proof-of-concept digital artefact. This is an achievable output, a discrete piece of work which will be completed in a relatively short space of time, using Open Source tools and techniques. The processes and workflows identified by the case study may provide tangible benefits for others in similar situations.

The sustainability challenges will be identified by way of a literature review, which will also consider the specifics of the Irish landscape. Some contemporaneous projects will be reviewed and approaches taken for similar ‘lost projects’ will be examined. The creation of the digital artefact will utilise Restoration and Repurposing methodology.

Figure 3 - Research Methodologies in Support of Research Problem. (Source: Author)

1.6 Scope and Limitations

The scope of this dissertation is to offer a practical solution for those facing challenges in creating sustainable digital Humanities projects, showing by example what is achievable using the tools and technologies available in 2022.

The epistemological crisis in the Humanities is not the focus of this research and sustainability challenges facing the Academy *per se* are beyond its scope. When Drucker considers whether digital projects in the Humanities are sustainable, she states that ‘the question can be answered by examining our work at multiple scales’ (2021, p.ii86) and this dissertation proposes to examine the issue at the individual project level. It takes as its focus issues of particular relevance to a database project, identified by Poole as one of the ‘ten modes of digital humanities work’ (2017, p.92).

The artefact creation will be constrained by my decision to use only tools that provide low barriers to access in terms of technical expertise and financial outlay; and which also operate within the parameters of Open Access, adhering to FAIR principles and Open Data guidelines, and using Open Source platforms and software.

1.7 Resources

The following tools and resources are used during the dissertation process.

Writing

The dissertation was written on a MacBook Air running macOS Monterey (v12.5), using the writing package Scrivener (v3.2.2, (*Scrivener*, n.d.)). All graphics and illustrations were created using Microsoft Powerpoint (v16.63.1), and MindMeister (basic) was used for some visualisations. Once created, all graphics, visualisations, diagrams, charts and screenshots were saved as .png files before being imported into the main body of the text. The final .pdf version was created using Microsoft Word (v16.63.1).

GoogleDocs (*Google Docs*, n.d.) and Microsoft Teams (*Microsoft Teams*, n.d.) were used for communications and resource sharing.

Literature Review

The resources available via the UCC library were used throughout this research to access online electronic journals, print books and the CORA repository. BASE (*BASE*, n.d.) was used as the primary search engine for the literature review, supported by others such as Google Scholar (*Google Scholar*, n.d.), Web of Science (*Clarivate*, n.d.) and Connected Papers (*Connected Papers*, n.d.). Zotero (v6.0.11) was used for reference management.

Digital Artefact

Resources and tools used for the creation of the digital artefact are described in detail in Chapter 3. They include: Omeka (v3.0.2) as content repository and dissemination tool, with Visual Studio Code (v1.27.2) and FileZilla (v3.60.1) for file manipulation and management. For data management, cleansing and analysis MDBdecode (v1.4), Excel (16.63.1) and OpenRefine (v3.5.2) were used. Web-hosting was provided by Reclaim (*Reclaim Hosting*, n.d.).

Digital Archiving

Digital resources were archived using the Internet Archive (*Internet Archive: Wayback Machine*, n.d.) and WARC files were created and validated using Webrecorder's suite of Open Source tools (*Webrecorder*, n.d.). Material was deposited in a GitHub (*GitHub*, n.d.) repository. See Digital Manifest for further information on preservation and dissemination platforms used.

1.8 Organisation of the Dissertation

Figure 4 - Structure of the Dissertation. (Source: Author)

Chapter One gives an introduction to the research topic and presents the research objectives, methodologies, resources, scope and limitations.

Chapter Two provides a review of the literature in the area of digital sustainability in the Humanities. It begins with an overview of digital aspects of Humanities scholarship, and then identifies sustainability challenges in digital projects. It addresses key topics in the context of the Irish Humanities landscape and concludes with an examination of contemporaneous projects and ongoing recovery efforts for legacy digital Humanities projects.

Chapter Three outlines the reasons for selecting the Munster Women Writers project as a case study and the approach that will be taken to (re)create the digital artefact using Restoration and Repurposing. It also outlines the tools and technologies proposed for this purpose.

Chapter Four documents the design and implementation process for the artefact creation. The artefact in this case will be an Omeka resource presenting a subset of data from the original MWW dataset, in addition to ancillary materials which are no longer available in the digital realm.

Chapter Five analyses and evaluates the major findings of the artefact creation and contextualises these with reference to the sustainability challenges as outlined in the literature review.

Chapter Six reflects on the dissertation process and its outputs, and makes suggestions for future work.

The Appendices provide additional resources for future researchers including a data dictionary for the MWW original dataset, and most importantly as an accessible output from this thesis, guidelines for others undertaking similar recovery projects. They also provide a detailed visualisation of the Irish digital landscape, as at August 2022; Omeka data mappings; and technical details of systems, plugins and versions used.

The digital artefact is available at the following location:

<https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/>

An archived version of the digital artefact can be viewed on the Internet Archive accessible using the following permanent link:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20220805115257/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/>

1.9 Conclusion

This chapter presented the research problem as the challenge of sustainability for digital Humanities projects in Ireland. It established two clear research objectives through which the research problem could be investigated.

1. The identification of key issues for Irish digital Humanities projects
2. The creation of a proof-of-concept digital artefact

The methodologies outlined to support this research in addressing the objectives comprise a Literature Review and a Case Study using Restoration and Repurposing.

Information on the resources to be used were outlined, and the limitations and scope of the research were discussed. The chapter concluded with an overview of the dissertation structure. A summary of the research project is provided (Fig. 5) below.

Figure 5 - Research Summary. (Source: Author)

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter will explore the literature on the topic of sustainability in digital humanities. It will provide a brief overview of digital aspects of Humanities scholarship and consider the overlap with the discrete academic discipline of Digital Humanities. Having established a clear understanding of ‘digital Humanities’ as the context of this dissertation it will seek to identify sustainability challenges in digital projects. There will follow a review of projects contemporaneous to MWW and efforts elsewhere to achieve sustainability for legacy digital projects. It will conclude with an examination of key sustainability challenges situating them within the Irish digital Humanities landscape.

2.2 The (Digital) Humanities

Piotrowski (2018) suggests that the ‘digital’ of Digital Humanities ‘really means “belonging to the digital age,” i.e., modern or contemporary’ and in a later paper he proposes two schools within DH: those who see the discipline as the study of humanities using contemporary tools, and those who view DH as the ‘development and application of a new computational methodology in the humanities’ (Piotrowski, 2020). For this latter group his solution is to propose a new term under which they should cluster - Computational Humanities. While the debate around a precise definition for DH continues (Gold and Klein, 2019), there is no denying that ‘Everyone in academia now accepts that DH is something’ albeit with the caveat that ‘not everyone appreciates or agrees upon what that thing might include’ (Murphy *et al.*, 2020).

In this research paper I propose to be inclusive in my understanding of DH and encompass scholars in the ‘traditional’ humanities, embracing the first rule of the DH social contract ‘the notion of niceness or civility’ (Koh, 2014). These humanist scholars, who may not define themselves as digital humanists, use technology to gather, create, and disseminate knowledge. In doing so I concur with Pannacker’s view that ‘Digital humanities is a comprehensive activist project that uses technology to respond to the interconnected cultural and structural problems of academe’ (2011). McGinnis (2019) asserts that the application of digital tools adds extensibility to traditional

humanities projects, while Edmond notes that DH method and tools are ‘ever more commonplace’ (2016, p.56).

As the research funding landscape, particularly in a European context, seeks to provide greater accountability and transparency in exchange for the significant public funds that the pursuit of knowledge requires few, if any, scholars now find themselves in a position where engagement with digital technology is absent. Horizon, the EU’s main research funding stream stipulates ‘Mandatory open access to publications and open science principles... throughout the programme’ (Horizon Europe, n.d.). Adherence to FAIR Principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016; Hodson *et al.*, 2018) and the Open Data Directive (EU, 2019) are being placed front and centre of current and future research. Humanists, digital or otherwise, are now bound to participate in ‘the everyday activities of the digital age’ (Murphy *et al.*, 2020).

While the application of the FAIR Principles for publications and datasets may be relatively straightforward, there are significant challenges for the Humanities where artefacts such as websites, apps, games, images, sounds, virtual objects, experiences and art-works are routinely generated. Ramsey’s aim may have been provocation when he stated ‘Personally, I think Digital Humanities is about building things’ (2011) but there is no doubt that the knowledge ‘output’ of the discipline has provided the Academy with many challenges to its traditional practices.

2.3 The digital Humanities in Ireland

The use of digital tools in the Humanities in Ireland stretch back to the ‘late eighties, certainly the early nineties’ (Murphy *et al.* 2020, p.169) and its beginnings are closely associated with Peter Flynn, the then webmaster at UCC, who along with UCC historian Donnchadh Ó Corráin, created the one of the world’s first DH projects CELT (CELT, n.d.). In his comprehensive overview of DH in Ireland O’Sullivan (2020) notes the many parallels between the goals of Flynn and Ó Corráin and those of the Women Writers Project which was underway at Brown University at the time, under the direction of Susanne Woods. For his part Flynn acknowledged the input of Professor Marianne McDonald, University of California, San Diego, a funder of the *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae*, (TLG, n.d.) and Elaine Brennan, of the Women Writers Project, on the development of CELT. The UCC project, also supported by the Royal Irish Academy (RIA) came

to be known as CURIA (an acronym derived from Cork University and Royal Irish Academy) and its first document was published online in 1993 (Ahlstrom, 2014; Flynn, 2017).

The humanities continued to employ digital tools and techniques but it wasn't until 2007 that Ireland could lay claim to the creation of its own digital humanities space - the Digital Humanities Observatory (DHO) - the first concrete attempt at coordinating the efforts and harnessing the output of digital Humanities projects. DHO created and managed the first repository for digital Humanities projects, DRAPier. A recipient of major government funding, DHO and DRAPier were an attempt to bring coherence to the digital landscape but, unfortunately, fell foul of the recession that followed the financial crisis of 2008 (Keating, 2014; Murphy *et al.*, 2020).

Kelleher and Conroy (2014, p.x) review the Irish landscape since the establishment of the Humanities Serving Irish Society (HSIS) consortium in 2008 and assert the importance of 'recognizing (sic) the value of different 'outputs', 'deliverables' and 'performance indicators', and of reflecting consciously on the appropriateness of modes of funding, assessment and evaluation, and even of terminology'. Underlining the importance of a humanities-focussed national body, the HSIS consortium looks to the Irish Humanities Alliance (IHA) to continue its work. This sense of hope was echoed by the DHO in its 'Goodbye and thanks' post (DHO, 2013) stating that 'The investment in HSIS and the DHO has put Irish humanities scholars in a solid position to continue to grow this valuable community and allow it to flourish in the future'.

Officially launched in 2015, the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) began its work in 2011, and was involved in the operation of a structured PhD in Digital Arts and Humanities programme which funded 15 scholars (*DRI*, 2002). Largely because of this investment in the early 2010s many of Ireland's third-level Institutions now have centres that focus on DH and cultural analytics. However, to this day 'the Irish DH community is one comprised of individuals rather than institutions: people are working together, but they are doing so without much of a formal national framework' (O'Sullivan, 2020, p.14).

Since the demise of DRAPier there is no longer any single portal through which to access Irish digital Humanities output. At time of writing, and despite a statement on the RIA's DHO website

that the ‘necessary files to enable individuals to run this site themselves are available as a downloadable zip’, the files are no longer accessible.

A number of projects which DRAPier hosted are identified by O’Sullivan in his *Digital Humanities in Ireland* (2020) where he notes that database projects are the dominant force in Ireland, observing a marked absence of analytics endeavours over the previous 20 years in the broad DH field. It is worth noting that since the publication of his paper both *Project Victeur* (2022) and *Contagion* (2022), situated squarely in the field of Cultural Analytics, are underway, both based in UCD’s Centre for Cultural Analytics.

The fragmented nature and complexities of the Irish landscape are examined later in this chapter through the lens of challenges to sustainability for the digital Humanities in Ireland.

See Appendix A for a detailed overview of the digital Humanities landscape in Ireland today.

2.4 Sustainability Challenges

Lemenager and Foote (2012) state that while sustainability is often seen as an economic issue linked with production, resources, ecology and the environment, it should be understood much more broadly than that, and in McKibben’s (2010) view it is a concept with a ‘squishy’ nature. The sustainability challenge associated with embracing digital technologies clearly has implications for the environment, from the energy consumption of data centres (CSO, 2022) to the mining of precious metals for computer chips (Belton, 2021). Work is being done within the sector via the Digital Humanities Climate Coalition (DHCC, 2022) to provide guidance and advice on designing projects within a climate justice-oriented framework.

Dombrowski (2014) provides an excellent contribution to the literature with a case study of Project Bamboo, a DH project which ended in 2012 having failed to achieve its goals of developing an infrastructure and support framework for shared technology service in the arts and humanities. Technical challenges, scope creep, failure to agree sustainability plans and operating models until phase two (after key technical decisions were made) and a lack of buy-in from the academic community were all contributing factors to its demise. Dombrowski suggests that the biggest

impediment was the absence of a shared vision among project leaders, development teams, and communications staff at the development and implementation phases with a ‘silo’ mentality prevailing. The project failed to define itself clearly and ‘without this shared vision it became little more than a funding umbrella for individual initiatives’ (Ibid., p.335).

Drucker (2021) writes compellingly in her paper about the challenges to sustainability for DH and argues that a sustainable system should be recognised as having many of the defining attributes of a complex system ‘non-linear, probabilistic, and nondeterministic’ (Ibid., p.ii86). She considers sustainability through the lens of issues that arise at the project level such as ‘infrastructure dependency, platform design, intellectual frameworks, community buy-in, and obsolescence of plugin functionality’ (Ibid., p.xx87) to the wider challenges of complex relationships between both individuals and disciplines. She observes a tension between the needs of individual projects and those of the host institutions, and the repositories in which the projects may be aggregated. Sustainability in terms of the intellectual agenda is also a consideration and she cites the *Orlando* project (*Orlando Project*, n.d.), as a case in point, where the feminist approach to encoding of the original texts has had to be reconsidered in light of Linked Open Data (*Orlando 2.0*, n.d.). At inter/national level many projects are invisible to online catalogues (i.e. WorldCat); the lack of central index/repository for digital projects renders many invisible and therefore inaccessible. This silo approach to DH can lead to stylistic dissonance where ‘an old interface causes students, for instance, to characterise sites as ‘so 1990s’ (Ibid., p.xx91). She concludes by addressing the intellectual considerations of sustainability in the context of knowledge production as a ‘complex epistemological object’ (Ibid., p.xx91).

Edmond and Morselli’s (2020) review of the Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure (CENDARI) project proposes five high-level principles to engender sustainability, which that project defined concisely as ‘optimised for reuse’ (Edmond and Morselli, p.1029). They view the issue of sustainability as a publication and documentation challenge and acknowledge that the term, whilst increasingly prominent in the discourse, is often presented without a clear consensus as to its meaning. They look to research undertaken in the Library and Information Science realm as formative in their understanding of the word, and point to a significant meta-analysis of the literature by Eschenfelder *et al.* (2019) which defines sustainability as the continued

operation of a collection, service, or organisation related to digital libraries, archives and repositories over time. This, they propose, requires consideration not only of technical issues such as formats, standards, platforms and infrastructures, but also the less tangible aspects of ‘community, communications and process knowledge’ (Edmond and Morselli, 2020, p.1019).

While the CENDARI project (*Cendari*, n.d.), which was built from 2012-2016, predates the explicit Open Science and FAIR Data agendas of more recent times, it embraced both and remains an exemplar of its kind. The key finding of the *White Book of Archives* (Beneš *et al.*, 2016) produced by the project to both summarise its operations and offer advice and insight, is a recommendation that institutions use formats that conform to international standards to facilitate active engagement with modern technologies and methodologies.

Kálmán *et al.* (2019) give a comprehensive snapshot of the largely heterogenous DH landscape across the EU, identifying the complex nature of resource sharing in the multidisciplinary, multinational DH landscape. They cite the FAIR principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016) and the need to support metadata standards with appropriate technical infrastructures in trusted repositories; accessibility - via both aggregation and use of protocols such as OAI-PMH; interoperability (via APIs), and clear policies, as being key sustainability. The reference of the need to ‘establish academic gratification for the creation and publication of research data and software’ (Kálmán *et al.*, p.114) is significant, alluding as it does to the need for a shift in the way that the Academy views and values DH output.

As can be seen from this review of the sustainability literature it is a topic of great complexity encompassing issues of access, availability, longevity, funding and policy/vision. It is also an issue worthy of epistemological and intellectual interrogation.

2.5 Contemporaneous Projects

The Munster Women Writers (MWW) Project was not alone in its aspiration to make available information on female writers rendered invisible in the literary canon of the 1990s. At the same time as work was being undertaken on the MWW project, the Women in Modern Irish Culture (WiMIC) project was being developed in UCD, led by Maria Luddy and Gerardine Meaney.

The WiMIC project concluded in 2006 when the website went live, with a commitment to maintain the database online for 10 years after project completion and the project was accessible on DRAPler until 2013. After a period of outage in 2017/18 WiMIC was restored on a ‘best effort’ basis by the Digital Humanities department in Warwick University (*Women in Modern Irish Culture*, n.d.). Unfortunately it is off-line at time of writing, for technical reasons. [Note: In response to the author’s enquiries, Warwick University’s IT department stated that ‘The developer of the relaunched site no longer works for us’.]

Two other major contemporary projects, often cited as exemplars (Wernimont, 2013) focussed on making texts of women writers accessible. Both published a print version concurrent with the development of the online resource, and both now sadly have opted to reside behind paywalls, surely at odds with their original visibility and accessibility objectives.

In 1994 the Brown University Women Writers Project was established to create a ‘textbase that will secure these women's place in literary history and for the future of humanities scholarship’ (*Women Writers Online*, n.d.) focussing on women writing in the English language from 1350-1850. In addition to a print version, the database (which contained full texts as well as biographical information) was made available online, following encoding of the originally gathered texts using TEI, in 1999. It is a project that has moved variously between internal university departments (English, to Computing, to Scholarly Technology, to the library’s Centre for Digital Scholarship) and institution - in 2013 it moved from Brown University to Northeastern University, where it now resides in the Digital Scholarship Group in NU’s library. (Woods, 1994; *Women Writers Online*, n.d.).

The scope of the *Orlando* project which received funding in 1995, was the literary history of women writers from the British Isles, from earliest times to the present day and the project produced both print volumes and an ‘electronic text base’ (Brown *et al.*, 2007; Ballaster *et al.*, 2019). The content was encoded using SGML, later XML, and key to the project was the semantic tagging it employed (*Orlando*, n.d.) enabling forms of non-linear searching previously inaccessible to the print-based researcher. The original project went live as a searchable database in 2006 and

this year the project has been re-launched as ‘Orlando 2.0’ - with a new interface in an effort to improve the searchability of the database, and a move into the realm of Linked Open Data.

2.6 Practical Approaches

The literature on the topic has a strong theoretical focus on the issue of sustainability, and what can, and should be done for future projects. There is an absence of case studies where tools and methods have been employed or proposed to address smaller legacy DH projects. Research that has been documented tends to come from research in the LIS domain such as Matusiak *et al.* (2017) with its focus on preserving and making accessible an oral history archive using Omeka, and Kemp *et al.* (2019) addressing the preservation and maintenance issues involved in managing a legacy blog archive using WordPress and flat file web archiving tools. Antonin *et al.* (2020) propose that legacy projects fall in to two separate categories, namely Restoration projects and Repurposing projects, which necessitate differing approaches.

This dissertation takes as a case study the Munster Women Writers (MWW) Project initiated in 1999, and is mindful of the dozens of similar projects that have been ‘lost’ in the intervening years; but it is also concerned with how future projects can avoid such a fate, to ensure visibility and representation in the canon of Irish academia. The following two papers have examined such issues in depth.

Smithies *et al.* (2019) in reviewing the major archiving and sustainability project undertaken in King’s Digital Lab (KDL) in 2016/7 (c.100 projects) acknowledges the problem of sustaining DH projects beyond their initial lifecycle, making a distinction between projects requiring ‘intellectual, technical, and financial overhead of ongoing maintenance...[and those]...to be archived online for the historical record’ (Smithies *et al.*, 2019, p.26). The major output of the KDL endeavour has been the implementation of a robust Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC) process within King’s which ensures visibility of sustainability issues from project conception stage, acknowledging the funding requirements such a commitment brings. Maintenance and archiving is seen as an iterative and imperfect process, which can be greatly aided by project adherence to best practice in terms of metadata standards and technology/platform selection.

Sweeney *et al.* (2017) offer a case study of the approach taken by Northeastern University Libraries, where the challenge of sustainability is viewed as one that should be seen as a shared responsibility between the academic and library communities. Noting the strong link between data curation and publishing (Choudhury *et al.*, 2012; Muñoz, 2013) the university has created the Community Enhanced Repository for Engaged Scholarship (CERES, n.d.), in effect a digital repository and strategy comprising systems and tools, partnerships and support. Recognising that many of the projects at the university were being undertaken using open source tools they considered Drupal, Omeka, and WordPress as base platforms, selecting WordPress due to the wide range of customisation options and plugins, and its broad usage, and support, as an open source platform. Crucially, they developed custom plugins (APIs) to allow users to connect with data sources from their existing Fedora (Fedora, n.d.) institutional repository, and for the creation of maps, timelines and image viewers in WordPress. Alongside the tool infrastructure they developed policies and workflows and, key to the endeavour, have mandated a robust data management plan for all projects going forward.

2.7 The Irish Landscape

2.7.1 ‘What’ and ‘how’, ‘why’ and ‘for whom’?

While Irish voices make a meaningful contribution to the literature on an international level e.g. Trinity College Dublin’s Jennifer Edmond (Su and Zhang, 2022, Table 6), there is a marked absence in the literature about digital Humanities projects in an Irish context. The recent publication by the National Open Research Forum (NORF, 2021) provides an excellent overview of the Irish research landscape with a very clear focus on Open Access (OA), and while many of its recommendations and insights are applicable to outputs often associated with digital Humanities, such as database projects, it does not address the specific requirements of digital outputs.

The Irish Humanities Alliance in its *Looking Towards the Future* strategy document (2020) acknowledges the importance of Open Access but it falls far short of calling for any national strategy to facilitate such access, preferring to focus its call to action on a silo-based approach, to

‘Support the viability of publications that advance knowledge in highly specialised disciplines’. In an already fragmented DH landscape (O’Sullivan, 2020) this seems to be somewhat short-sighted.

Examining sustainability through the lens of infrastructures is a useful way to approach the topic if one concurs with Edmond and Morselli’s (2020) view that sustainability is a process, one which involves looking not only the ‘what’ and ‘how’, but also the ‘why’ and ‘for whom’ (p.1024).

Infrastructure is a nebulous term and in the context of the digital humanities Edmond (2016) identifies various usages, such as the physical technology layer of a data network or the intellectual research network of the academy. The RIA and NORF define research infrastructure as encompassing ‘equipment, facilities (including library resources), buildings, research institutes, research support systems, virtual infrastructure and personnel’ (RIA, 2018).

2.7.2 The Network

In terms of physical infrastructures Ireland’s research community relies on HEAnet to provide the national backbone network of 2500 km of fibre optic cable, operating at speeds of 100Gbit/s (*HEAnet*, n.d.), with resilient connections to other European and International research networks. It does not provide data management services or archival preservation facilities. The majority of third level institutions also operate their own data centres which facilitate ongoing research and provide hosting for the institutional repositories. HEAnet’s most recent strategic plan (*HEAnet Strategy*, n.d.) lists Research Engagement as a strategic objective with a stated goal being to ‘support Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)’. In June 2020 HEAnet appointed a Research Engagement Support officer and in March 2022 the process of establishing a National Research Support Forum commenced (the scoping of which is ongoing at time of writing).

2.7.3 Repositories

Ireland has no national repository for research data and the output of digital Humanities projects still depends on hosting at local level. While each of the third-level institutions has its own digital repository (see Appendix A2 - Open Access in Third Level) the contents are primarily text-based .pdfs, often publication pre-prints, made available in order to comply with conditions of research

funding. At a national level some digital repositories do exist, but they operate within very strict parameters such as the National Biodiversity Data Centre (*National Biodiversity Data Centre*, n.d.) or the Irish Social Science Data Archive (*Irish Social Science Data Archive*, n.d.) - which aggregates up to the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA). The silo nature of research repositories has led to ‘considerable inefficiency across the research system’ (NORF, 2021, p.58) and is ‘a major impediment to system-level monitoring, management and impact assessment’ according to the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (DFHERIS) in their *Innovation 2020* strategy document (2015).

The Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) is a repository with a national remit that encompasses Irish social and cultural data, including Humanities and Social Science research data as well as Cultural Heritage data, and it provides the data management and digital preservation services absent from HEAnet. As a national aggregator to *Europeana*, it makes Irish research visible on the European and International stage, facilitated by its adherence to FAIR principles and Dublin Core metadata standards. It is also a certified Trusted Digital Repository (one of only three in the country alongside UCD’s Digital Library and ISSDA) and works within the parameters of best practice for interoperability to facilitate OA for its hosted content.

It should be noted that in terms of national institutions the National Library of Ireland (*nli*, n.d.) has been selectively archiving Irish websites since 2011, although the effort seems to have been ad hoc until relatively recently. It started to curate collections in 2018 when it became a partner organisation of the Internet Archive (*Archive-It - National Library of Ireland*, n.d.). It has no specific digital remit and collects, in line with its generic Collection Development Policy, websites and social media accounts that are of Irish interest and publicly accessible. According to Kurzmeier *et al.* (2022, p.9) ‘The single biggest challenge is the legislation...[the NLI]...don't have a domain crawl’, the absence of legal deposit legislation for born-digital content in Ireland adds to the financial challenge the NLI faces in archiving web content. There is no facility to deposit WARC files independent of the NLI’s own efforts in this area.

2.7.4 Open Data and Open Access

The nature of Ireland's research repository infrastructure is a fragmented one, based primarily around third-level institutions and there is no clear national framework to offer advice, make recommendations or provide clear direction when it comes to issues such as interoperability, metadata standards or methodology best practice. Conditions of funding at both the European and national level demand adherence to the many EU policy recommendations such as those relating to Open Science (European Commission, 2018) and Open Data (European Commission, 2019). A key goal of the Commission is the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC, 2022) which will 'enable researchers across disciplines and countries to store, curate and share data'.

A number of national and International bodies have been established to provide focus for the sector as it seeks to align with both EU and national requirements in the era of Open Data. The establishment of NORF is one such attempt to address this gap. NORF is chaired jointly by the Higher Education Authority (HEA) and the Health Research Board (HRB) and is supported by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, and is based at the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI). While NORF has buy-in from the research sector, and has a clear remit to develop a coherent national framework, its work is still very much at the infancy stage. Ten years since the publication of Ireland's *National Principles on Open Access* and five years since the establishment of NORF, the forum has only recently (April, 2022) issued a draft of its National Action Plan for Open Research (NORF, 2022), building on the *National Framework for the Transition to an Open Research Environment, 2019*.

Open Access is one of the core principles that underpins research repositories but as noted in their *Landscape* report (NORF, 2021) 'the sustainability, archiving and long-term preservation capacity of institutional repositories is a concern'. While most adhere to the requirements for OA publications, few have signed up to FAIR principles, or are aligned with organisations or networks that promote adherence to the many standards that enable interoperability and preservation (such as content metadata, formats, platforms). Equally important is the application of standards at governance level, the 'shared vision' whose absence is identified by Dombrowski (2014) and

Drucker (2021) as a key reason for the failure of digital projects in their attempt to meet sustainability goals of access, availability and longevity.

2.7.5 Interoperability

Interoperability is dependent on compliance with standards, and the silo nature of Irish institutional repositories and academic disciplines continues to hinder their adoption at scale. In 2021 the Consortium of National And University Libraries (CONUL) established a Digital Scholarship group (*Digital Scholarship Network Ireland*, n.d.) with a remit to develop and deliver resources ‘to enable modern scholarship using digital methods, tools, or approaches’. At time of writing, however, the group has issued no publications. The DRI does provide direction in this regard and has produced a number of publications to assist researchers (titles include: Guide to Metadata Quality Control; Choosing CMS Technologies; Dublin Core and the DRI) all with the aim of helping their members comply with the standards and structures that underpin the interoperability functionality of their repositories.

2.7.6 Digital Data Literacy

Defined by Abner (2021) as ‘the ability to critically create, manipulate, manage, analyze, understand, and communicate data’ much has been written on the importance of digital data literacy in the Humanities (Calzada-Prado and Marzal, 2013; Koltay, 2015; 2017). Literature in the LIS field has identified the issue as posing a significant risk to sustainability ‘due to the adoption of inappropriate technologies and standards’ (Manoff *et al.*, (2013), quoted in Eschenfelder *et al.*, 2019, p.187). The RIA’s *Future Proofing and Improving Research Infrastructures* policy document makes 14 recommendations, and suggests there is an urgent need to ‘develop and implement a national plan for data management and open science across all institutions’ (RIA, 2018, p.6). HEAnet’s proposed National Research Support Forum may also contribute to the digital literacy effort, although the scope of the forum is unknown at time of writing. One of the key tenets of research is reproducibility, which allows scholars both to validate and to build on the work of others; this requires a level of data literacy for all, and according to O’Sullivan (2019, p.3) ‘Scholars with technical proficiencies have a responsibility to explain their methods clearly, while the less technical need to increase their familiarity with new practices’.

2.7.7 Peer Networks

The NORF *Landscape* report (2021) states that ‘peer support networks and communities of practice are underdeveloped or absent entirely in Ireland’ (p.51). The Irish Humanities Alliance (IHA) represents Humanities scholars in eleven institutions on the island of Ireland. However, as noted in section 2.5.1 above, it makes no mention of sustainability or digital tools/resources in its strategy or policy documents. This is despite four of the six ‘Impact Case Studies’ highlighted on the IHA website - *Alternative Belfast* (QUB), *Irish Famine Memorials* (UCD), *Letters of 1916* (Maynooth) and *The 1641 Depositions* (TCD), having very significant digital elements (*Impact Case Studies - Irish Humanities Alliance*, n.d.).

As well as the IHA, the DHO in their ‘Goodbye and thanks’ post (2013, see also section 2.3 above), welcomes Irish involvement in an ‘exciting’ new European ‘Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities’ (DARIAH) initiative. DARIAH has not, however, lived up to its potential, certainly not within the Irish context. Despite the assertion that ‘It preserves, provides access to and disseminates research...[...]...and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed’ (*DARIAH*, n.d.) the network has failed to establish itself in Ireland.

The most active peer organisation at time of writing is the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association (*UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Network*, n.d.) with a stated aim to critically interrogate ‘concepts of sustainability, inclusivity, training, [and] advocacy’ (*Ibid.*, *About*). Co-funded by the Irish Research Council it has produced four discussion papers, which are openly available on the Open Science Framework (OSF) platform (Winters, 2021). The discussion papers form the output of workshops held in 2020/21 on topics such as Capacity Enhancement, Promoting Diversity and Communicating the Value of DH. At the first session ‘it was noted that, in a context where innovation is valued above all, rewards (on the part of funders and of institutions) for sustainability and support are missing’ (UK-IRL DHN, 2021a, p.22) and at the second workshop ‘issues of sustainability and interoperability permeated the panel session’ (UK-IRL DHN, 2021b, p.10).

2.8 Conclusion

This literature review has presented a view of the digital humanities as a broad discipline, one which encompasses computational analytics, database projects and the wider adoption of digital tools and techniques in the traditional humanities. It has identified sustainability as a complex issue, with environmental, epistemological and practical components. It has examined projects contemporaneous to the MWW project and reviewed two similar legacy projects that addressed the sustainability challenge.

Through the lens of infrastructures, making reference to physical entities such as repositories and the network, OA policies and standards, digital literacy and peer organisations, it has reviewed some of the key issues in an Irish context.

The following chapters will propose a pathway to sustainability by asking what can practically be done for legacy digital projects in the Humanities, using *munsterwomen.ie*, the digital output of the Munster Women Writers project as a case study.

3. Epistemology and Methodology

3.1 Introduction

As stated previously, Ireland has no dedicated repository for the output of digital Humanities projects. Numbers of projects have been ‘lost’ for very many reasons: from changes in project personnel, to shifting institutional goals, lack of resources, an absence of infrastructure leading Drucker to note ‘the window of project sustainability will vary considerably depending on these many factors’ (2021, p.ii89). Much, if not all, of the support for these projects comes from public funding, via bodies such as the Higher Education Authority (HEA), the Irish Research Council (IRC) and educational institutions such as the universities. While effecting change at the national level is not within the remit of this dissertation I believe that by demonstrating one possible approach to (re)presenting a digital artefact, potential pathways for digital sustainability may be explored. The artefact that I have selected to (re)create is the digital element of the Munster Women Writers project, a searchable literary and bibliographical database, making it available on a publicly accessible website.

In this chapter I discuss the reasons for selecting this dataset and the methodology and methods I propose to use.

3.2 Epistemology

The Women in Irish Society Project (WISP) was one of the first Humanities projects with significant digital elements to be undertaken in Ireland but there remains little trace of it in the digital realm today. Led by Professor Patricia Coughlan, from UCC’s Department of English, it was awarded three-year PRTLI-1 funding in 1999 and was a multi-disciplinary project which took a collaborative approach to research. WISP had three strands: Irish Women at Work (*Irish Women at Work - Digital Repository of Ireland*, n.d.) - an Oral History project; Documenting Irish Feminisms (Connolly and O’Toole, 2005) - a critical analysis of feminism in Ireland, published in print form; and the Munster Women Writer’s Project (MWW) - a literary and bibliographic research project with both print and digital outputs.

A desk-based research project, the MWW data gathering was extensive and involved multiple researchers across the three-year funding period. It was led by Dr Tina O'Toole, who undertook the English-language research, assisted by two Irish-language scholars, Gearóidín Nic Carthaigh and Síle Ní Chochláin. The proposed outputs of the MWW project were a print book (published in 2005 as the *Dictionary of Munster Women Writers, 1800-2000*), and a digital resource in the form of a searchable database on a publicly-accessible website *munsterwomen.ie*. The purpose of both resources was to enable other scholars to access the data collected by the project team and use it as a basis for their own enquiry.

The searchable database element of the project was beset by many challenges, not uncommon at the time as university departments struggled to embrace technological developments. While the digital resource was not delivered within the original project timeframe, nor by those to whom it was tasked, it was eventually completed and was functional from 2007 until 2013.

I have selected the MWW dataset for my project as it represents a unique resource which is currently inaccessible digitally. It contains information which has the potential to provide a wealth of material for further study to make visible women in literary culture; furthermore, digital access to the data contributes to one of the original MWW project aims - 'the dictionary as a feminist recovery project' (O'Toole, 2005).

I was able to acquire all the files related to this part of the project through personal contact with Dr Tina O'Toole, who had been the project lead, and via her made contact with Jonathan Neville a volunteer on the project who had in a personal capacity - and most fortuitously for me - retained back-ups of both the database and all website-related content (stylesheets, images, .asp and .mdb files etc.).

The original dataset consists of c.560 writers and for this proof-of-concept I propose dealing with approximately 10% of the dataset, namely writers born in, or associated with, county Tipperary.

3.3 Methodology

This project will employ Case Study methodologies to address the research problem.

In terms of research methodologies little has been written about legacy digital Humanities projects, Antonini *et al.* (2020) identify two approaches: Restoration: ‘implementing remedial actions that ‘update’ the project to new contexts to preserve its function and role’ and Repurposing: ‘implementing actions that rethink the value of the project by finding it new purposes, functions and roles in new contexts’ (Ibid., p.2). From the field of computer science comes the concept of Reconstruction (Sablatura and Zhou, 2017), which is often undertaken as a forensic exercise in order to recreate databases follow security breaches. [Note: the Emulation approach (Appuswamy and Joguin, 2020) is also an option, however it requires software, hardware (and skills) beyond the scope of this project].

I have considered the key **inputs** to the project, namely: the knowledge gap it sought to fill; the project team’s goals and objectives; and the funder’s priorities. I am also mindful of the project’s key **outputs**: knowledge creation, research activities and the potential for new outcomes in terms of research and impact in the area of Irish women’s writing. Using the methodology of restoration I will recreate the functionality, although not the appearance, of the MWW database, using an Open Source tool Omeka, to make the content accessible again. Through the methodology of repurposing, I will make available ancillary files such as images, documentation, and screenshots from the original website, in Omeka as a resource for future researchers. Consideration will also be made for WARC and OAI requirements.

3.4 Tools and System Requirements

There are two distinct areas to be considered for the selection of tools to create the digital artefact. Those for Data Management - falling firmly within the methodology of Restoration - facilitating the selection, cleaning, (re)formatting and (re)structuring of the data; and those for repurposing - the multi-faceted tools employed by Content Management Systems for the presentation, dissemination, and accessibility of the resource.

The overriding consideration for my tool selection is that they demonstrate low barriers to access, both in terms of the technical expertise to create and administer, and the financial outlay required

to deploy them; and that they adhere to international metadata standards and follow sector best practice.

For Data Management I considered the following tools:

Google Sheets, (*Google Docs*, n.d.) which provides a free alternative to Excel, with similar functionality, although it requires a Google account, and is not open source.

Microsoft Excel (*Microsoft Excel*, n.d.), which whilst proprietary and available only on subscription, is ubiquitous.

OpenRefine (*OpenRefine*, n.d) a free Open Source tool for data wrangling, similar to a spreadsheet tool but with additional database-like functionality.

Tableau Prep Builder (*Tableau*, n.d.), a proprietary tool for the wrangling of data prior to use with the Tableau visualisation tool (available under a free student trial licence).

After considerable testing of all of the above I decided on a combination of OpenRefine (preferred for global changes where tracking was essential) and Microsoft Excel (my preference for sorting and structuring) as my Data Management tools, primarily because I have the necessary expertise to use them, and both are freely available to me.

When selecting the appropriate Content Management System (CMS) for this project I referred to the FAIR Principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016) and DRI's CMS selection guidelines (DRI, 2015). I drew up the following list of system requirements (Table 1):

Table 1 - CMS System Requirements

Area	Requirement
Archival and preservation	Repository with multi-format support and ability to allow addition of rich metadata.
Archival and preservation	Ability to curate and disseminate exhibits.
Archival and preservation	Suitable for website harvesting (OAI and WARC)
Search capabilities	To facilitate research; to be discoverable (OAI-PMH)
Import/Export	Ability to batch ingest from .csv
Import/Export	Ability to export data in commonly used formats (RSS, JSON, XML)
User friendly	Low barrier to entry in terms of engagement and access, for both administrators and end-users
Interoperability	Support for metadata standards (Dublin Core) Specifically with DRI/Europeana
Interoperability	Support for FAIR Principles
Support	Active user base
Support	Online support structure
Extensibility	Active API development community
Extensibility	Open Source

I considered a number of tools including Omeka, WordPress, Scalar, Drupal and also considered building a website from scratch. After some experimentation and a review of the literature (Cuenca and Kowaleski, 2018; *Which DH Tools Are Actually Used in Research?*, 2020 – see Fig.6 below) I selected Omeka (version 3.0.2), with a proven track record in the field (Puckett and Leslie, 2016; Hoyle, 2017; Marsh, 2017; Matusiak *et al.*, 2017) as the CMS. The ability to structure the content and provide description using Dublin Core is the fundamental advantage that Omeka has over all similar tools. There are three versions of Omeka S (enterprise level) Classic (single exhibit, hosted by owner) and Net (hosted by Omeka, limited customisation). I have selected Omeka Classic as the CMS.

Figure 6 - DH Research Tools. (Source: <https://weltliteratur.net/dh-tools-used-in-research/>)

3.5 Conclusion

The selection of this dataset addresses a number of key sustainability issues. The initial project was publicly funded data collection, created primarily by women as one of the earliest digital Humanities projects in Ireland, to enhance visibility of minority writers: regional, female and Irish-language.

The methodologies have been selected to honour the original project's integrity and identity with a combined approach of Restoration and Repurposing; with tool selection focussed heavily on supporting FAIR principles and sector best practice.

The methodologies and tools proposed are accessible and achievable, even for those with little technical expertise and limited resources. In combination with the workflows outlined in the next chapter the approach proposed could be developed and enhanced for the re-creation of similar 'lost' projects and could also serve as a guide for current and future Humanities projects with digital elements.

4. Design and Implementation

4.1 Introduction

The objective of my dissertation is to make accessible the data of the MWW project, in line with FAIR Principles, Open Data guidelines and sector best practices. The output that will enable me to achieve this aim will be a Dublin Core-compliant, OAI-harvestable Omeka resource suitable for web archiving.

With the goal of this case study being to return data gathered by the project to the digital domain after a hiatus of nine years, I decided to focus on the content of the database itself, rather than on recreating the original website functionality or appearance (Fig. 7).

Figure 7 –Original munsterwomen.ie landing page. (Source: Author's personal archive)

I intend to use Omeka to:

- 1 (re)present data gathered by the MWW project
- 2 provide a brief history of the MWW project, images from the original project website, and an overview of the processes undertaken in this case study
- 3 present a Dublin Core-compliant resource that is searchable using OAI protocols and suitable for web archiving and aggregation by DRI/Europeana.

The (re)creation and (re)presentation of the data from the MWW project is a highly iterative process; consequently I propose to combine both design and implementation elements within this chapter, following the high-level workflows stages. These workflow stages document the design decisions taken around initial data preparation; content management system considerations (ingest, metadata, structures, collections/exhibits, maps etc.); and preparation of dataset suitable for OA deposit and web-archiving. Mindful of the value to future researchers I will provide screenshots of these processes and my progression in this chapter, to position this project firmly in the landscape of the tools and technologies available to me at this time.

A prerequisite to the installation of any CMS, such as Omeka, is access to a server on which both the application and content files can be hosted, stored and managed. For the development of this artefact I will be using the Reclaim Hosting (*Reclaim Hosting*, n.d.) service, which provides me with domain name registration, 2GB of server space, access to a range of applications (CMSs, DBs etc.), as well as file and server management tools. The steps for a CMS install will not be documented here as it is outside the scope of this project.

4.2 Workflow Stage 0 - Data Acquisition

I was able to acquire all the files related to the digital output of the MWW project from Jonathan Neville who, in a personal capacity as a volunteer on the project, had retained back-ups of the website-related content (stylesheets, images, .asp and .mdb files (Fig. 8)) which were originally coded c.2003. He shared this with me as a .rar file using Google Drive.

Figure 8 – Munsterwomen RAR Drive. (Source: Author Screenshot)

In addition to saving the data to my own device and two cloud storage providers (Dropbox and Google Drive), I also shared Jonathan’s link with former MWW project team members, and some former colleagues, now working in an institutional repository. This practical step ensures that the data from the MWW is now available, albeit not publicly accessible, to multiple people and in multiple locations: a small, but important, first step on the road to its sustainability.

Figure 9 – Munsterwomen RAR Drive DB files. (Source: Author Screenshot)

As can be seen from the contents of the .rar (Fig. 9, above) the files and folders arrived to me with no explanatory documentation. It seemed obvious that the database itself was contained within the _db_ folder, given its large size (14MB) relative to the other folders, but when I viewed the contents there were five possible versions available, all 3MB in size. Following enquiries to Jonathan and others there was no recollection from the team as to which version was the one used on the website between 2007 and 2013. As I don't have the appropriate software to view the dataset from the proprietary legacy database, Microsoft Access, I was unable to check for more detailed date:time stamps, I selected the one whose name indicated that it might be the most up-to-date: UCC_Database_irish_duplicate_gone_ver1_post_changes.mdb Nov 29, 2007 3MB

In order to view the data, I extracted the .mdb files using a free online tool MDB Opener (*Online Access DB Opener*, n.d.) this was my first view of the actual database files (Fig. 10).

id	proci...	Extent_Of_Work	Author_Analytic	Author_Role1	Author_Affili...	Title_Analytic	Medium_Design...	Connective_...	Author_Monogr...	Author_Role2	Title_Monographic	Journal_Title	Journal_Title_Wi...	Journal_Title_Wi...	Title
1	10	1896-1982	Barrington, M...												
2	2350	Contemporary	O'Higgins, Mal												
3	110						Historical fiction		Jacob, Rosam...		The Rebel's...				
4	40						Short stories		Barrington, M...		David's Daug...				
5	70		Barrington, M...			The Funeral	Short story					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
6	60		Barrington, M...			The Death of...	Short story					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
7	80		Barrington, M...			A Writer's Da...	Memoir					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
8	90		Barrington, M...			Spider in Love	Short story					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
9	100		Barrington, M...			The Corbies	Essay					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
10	110		Barrington, M...			Fable	Essay					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
11	120		Barrington, M...			The Bishop's...	Short story					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
12	1020		O'Faolain, Sean			Rev. of We ar...						The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
13	14350		Deevy, Teresa			Katie Roche	Play					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
14	15220		Deevy, Teresa			A Disciple	Play					Dublin Magazine	Dublin Magazine	Dublin Magazine	
15	1120		O Britain, Séán	prod.			Radio play					Shyllag	Shyllag	Shyllag	
16	13870		Styles, William	prod.			Radio play					Carolan's Cap	Carolan's Cap	Carolan's Cap	
17	16000		Deevy, Teresa			Rev. of Teresa...	Review					Irish Writing	Irish Writing	Irish Writing	
18	14370		Deevy, Teresa			Temporal Pow...	Play					Irish Writing	Irish Writing	Irish Writing	
19	13440		Terry Prone	interviewer	Interview...		Radio progra...		Patricia Lynch			Here and Now	Here and Now	Here and Now	
20	14380		Deevy, Teresa			A Disciple	Play								
21	14390		Deevy, Teresa			The Reapers	Play								
22	14400		Deevy, Teresa			Light Falling	Play								
23	15990		Deevy, Teresa			Strange Birth	Play								
24	16010		T.S.			Rev. of The Kl...						Irish Writing	Irish Writing	Irish Writing	
25	3090						Novel		Barrington, M...		My Cousin Ju...				
26	12770		O Conluain, P...	prod.	Contributor		Documentary...					I Stand the Se...	I Stand Self-D...	I Stand the Se...	
27	16020						Social history		Conyers, Dor...		Sporting Remi...				
28	1990		O'Faolain, Eileen			Galway Hats	Journalism					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
29	2000		O'Faolain, Eileen			Stockings for...	Journalism					The Bell	Bell	The Bell	
30	2280					Children's wri...			O'Faolain, Eileen		The Fairy Hen				
31	2170					Children's wri...			O'Faolain, Eileen		Miss Pennyfe...				
32	330	fl. 1945-1984	Brennan, Eliza...												
33	2180					Children's wri...			O'Faolain, Eileen		Miss Pennyfe...				
34	350					Novel			Brennan, Eliza...		Out of the Da...				
35	360					Children's wri...			Brennan, Eliza...		The Wind Fairies				
36	370					Novel			Brennan, Eliza...		Am I My Broth...				
37	380					Novel			Brennan, Eliza...		Whispering W...				
38	390					Children's wri...			Brennan, Eliza...		The Wind Fair...				
39	400					Children's wri...			Brennan, Eliza...		The Mystery...				
40	410					Poetry			Brennan, Eliza...		Wind over the...				

Figure 10 - MDB First View. (Source: MDB Screenshot)

4.3 Workflow Stage 1 - Data Preparation for Omeka

I exported this file from MDB Opener as a single .csv file to my desktop and opened it using MS Excel, saving it as a .csv to my MWW project folder. I also saved it as a .xlsx file, as prompted by

the application, however this resulted in the corruption of the formatting (as a result of the Irish-language fada). I reimported from .csv and saved as .xls (Excel legacy format) in order to retain the formatting. All future references to the Excel file are to the legacy .xls format. These two versions (.csv and .xls) were created as a safety back-up for myself before I began working with the data and are now saved to my own archive folder on DropBox.

Master safety files [**filename: MDBOpener_extractedMaster_MWW_Databaset.csv; and .xls**]

OpenRefine

To get an overview of the data I opened the .csv file using OpenRefine, setting the following parameters (Fig. 11) at ingest. It identified 49 columns and 3917 rows/records. All fields were text strings.

The screenshot shows the OpenRefine settings for parsing a CSV file. The 'Parse data as' section is set to 'CSV / TSV / separator-based files'. The 'Character encoding' is 'UTF-8'. The 'Columns are separated by' section has 'commas (CSV)' selected. The 'Trim leading & trailing whitespace from strings' checkbox is checked. The 'Column names (comma separated):' field is empty. The 'Use \" to enclose cells containing column separators' checkbox is checked. The 'Store blank cells as nulls' checkbox is checked.

Figure 11 - OpenRefine Settings. (Source: OpenRefine Screenshot)

Filtering the data established that each field/column was populated with at least one value, this meant that I could not immediately remove any columns without removing some data; it also allowed me to see that the dataset included multiple empty cells.

Author_Affiliation	3747	Call_Number	3917
Author_Role1	3667	ISSN	3917
Issue_ID	3613	Series_Issue_ID	3917
Place_Of_Birth	3507	Reprint_Status	3915
Author_Role2	3484	Series_Editor_Role	3915
Date_Of_Copyright	3414	Availiability	3914
Place_Of_Association	3410	ISBN	3913
Extent_Of_Work	3387	CODEN	3909
Connective_Phrase2	3375	Series_Editor	3908
Notes	3357	Location_URL	3905
Volume_ID	3357	Series_Volume_ID	3894
Journal_Title	3246	Series_Title	3876
Journal_Title_Without_An	3246	Document_Type	3874
Journal_Title_Without_The	3246	Author_Role3	3865
Location_In_Work	3230	Title	3859
Title_Analytic	2912	Edition	3847
Author_Analytic	2239	Author_Subsiary	3826
Place_Of_Publication	1466	Place_Of_Meeting	3826
Publisher_Name	1448	Connective_Phrase1	3810
Author_Monographic	1423	Report_ID	3807
Title_Monographic	1364	Abstract	3791
Medium_Designator1	1117	Author_Affiliation	3747
Date_Of_Publication	1028	Author_Role1	3667
Medium_Designator2	75	Issue_ID	3613
Packaging_Method	12	Place_Of_Birth	3507
Keywords	1	Author_Role2	3484
		Date_Of_Copyright	3414
		Place_Of_Association	3410

Figure 12 - Facet Filter Results. (Source: OpenRefine Screenshot)

Using a combination of desk-based research, and making reference to the print edition, I created a data dictionary in Excel with descriptions of fields, in advance of any data manipulation. This formed the basis of my data mapping document as I cleaned the data. I also assigned a numerical reference to each field, to aid identification.

Table 2 is an extract from the data dictionary showing the most significant fields, see Appendix C MWW Data Dictionary for complete list.

Table 2 - Extract from Data Dictionary

ID	Field Name	Description	Entries	Sample text	Notes
3	Extent_Of_Work	Dates associated with the writer	530	1896-1982	Inconsistent in terms of specificity, includes entries b-d, b only, d only; fl. (the years in which the writer was popular); Contemporary, and null
32	Place_Of_Birth	Place of birth of the writer	411	West Cork.	Inconsistent in terms of specificity, ranges from county to parish. Multiple format/spelling errors
33	Place_Of_Association	Place of association of the writer	507	Clonmel	Can contain multiple place names; inconsistent in terms of specificity, ranges from county to parish.
40	Connective_Phrase2	All genres associated with writer	542	Novels, Short Stories, Poetry	Links with Notes field. Contains multiple values separated by commas, all genres assoc with writer.
46	Notes	Biographical Summary	560	Born in a small village in Tipp	Free text, varying levels of detail
49	Keywords	Name of writer	3917	Barrington, Margaret	This was the key field in the dataset. The only place linking all bibliographical entries with writer.

Initial appraisal of the spreadsheet showed that each row represents a writer OR a bibliographic item (i.e. monograph, journal article, short story etc.). The rows were not grouped in any logical sense and the only way to link a writer with a bibliographic entry was by using Column 49: Keywords, which is populated for every row and contains the writer's name (Fig. 13). Column 46: Notes contains the biographical data for each writer.

h	Keywords	Notes	id	proclite_id	Extent_Of_Work	Author_Analytic	Author_Role1	Author_Affiliation	Title_Analytic	Medium_Designator1	Connective_Phrase1	Author_Monographic	Author_Role2	Title_Monographic	Journal_Title	Journal_Title_Without_The
	Barrington, Margaret		25	3090						Novel		Barrington, Margaret		My Cousin Justin		
	O'Faolain, Eileen		26	12770		O Conlain, Proinsias	prod.	Contributor		Documentary about James Joyce					I Stand the Self-Doomed, Unafraid	I Stand Self-Doomed, Unafraid
	Conyers, Dorothea		27	16020						Social history		Conyers, Dorothea		Sporting Reminiscences		
	O'Faolain, Eileen		28	1990		O'Faolain, Eileen			Gateway Hats	Journalism					The Bell	Bell
	O'Faolain, Eileen		29	2000		O'Faolain, Eileen			Storkings for Christmas	Journalism					The Bell	Bell
	O'Faolain, Eileen		30	2280					Children's writing			O'Faolain, Eileen		The Fairy Hen		
	O'Faolain, Eileen		31	2170					Children's writing			O'Faolain, Eileen		Miss Pennyfather and the Pooks		

Figure 13 - OpenRefine Keyword As Link. (Source: OpenRefine Screenshot)

I undertook various data cleansing actions in OpenRefine, using the facet/filter functionality. This was particularly useful for two tasks: the *Clustering* function enabled identification of spelling variations and standardisation of same. The *Column split* function allowed for creation of separate Birth and Death date fields from the date range.

Remove non-Biographical Rows

For the purposes of the Omeka artefact, which I propose as a proof-of-concept project, I used a subset of the available data. Given the complexity of the spreadsheet (relational data now in flat file format), and the detailed work required to rebuild it in order to align bibliographic with biographical information, I created a subset of data initially, extracting only those rows with biographical information.

Sorting on Column 46: Notes field

Exclude - blanks 560

[GREL: isBlank(value)=FALSE]

Exclude duplicates 554

[GREL: facetCount(value, 'value', 'Notes') > 1]

Identify Tipperary associated writers

The dataset contains 554 writers. I intended to select only a subset of the data, writers associated with county Tipperary. This was a time-consuming process as there was no consistency about the content in the location fields (32: Place_Of_Birth, 33: Place_Of_Association) - some place names were given as county only, some as townland, some contained multiple locations. It should also be noted that as the dictionary contains both English and Irish language entries, some place names required translation.

Sorting on Column 49: Keywords by text a-z (puts writers in alphabetical order)

Facet search and cluster on 32: Place_Of_Birth, 33: Place_Of_Association (used Key collision and nearest neighbour).

506 entries had data in Column 33: Place_Of_Association, additional 34 had data in 32: Place_Of_Birth, additional 8 had data in 46: Notes, 6 had no data (undertook desk research to identify place of association).

Following this I removed 493 rows relating to writers not associated with county Tipperary, as they would not require import to Omeka, at this time.

I exported my new dataset as [filename: MWW_TippOnly_PostRefine.csv].

4.4 Workflow Stage 2 - Creating the Omeka Resource

After checking the data for anomalies and errors my master spreadsheet consisted of a subset of data relating to 61 writers associated with county Tipperary. All writers will be represented in Omeka as a single item (entity), with associated elements (attributes). In addition to the 15 default Dublin Core metadata elements associated with the DC item-type, there are 16 additional item-types in Omeka (such as Person, Physical Object, Dataset, Moving Image, etc.) each with their own pre-defined elements, and the facility to add custom elements to each; it is also possible to create additional item-types. [Note: In ER terms ‘Item’ = ‘Entity’ and ‘Element’ = ‘Attribute’]

Metadata Selection

Metadata, often described as ‘data about data’, is information about an object. It describes the content and the context of an object, examples of metadata for a book might include the *title*, the *date* and *place* of publication and the *author* name. A metadata standard is an agreed set of such terms, which allows for different objects to be described in a similar way. There are many different metadata standards but one of the simplest, most flexible and most commonly used is called Dublin Core which is used across a wide range of domains.

A key consideration for the selection of Omeka for the creation of my digital artefact is its use of the 15 Dublin Core metadata elements (Fig. 14). I retained all these elements for each item,

although I did not populate each with a value at this stage. I am also able to change the order of the elements when the record is displayed to the user (the order can be revised at any point in the lifecycle of the artefact, using Admin tools).

Figure 14 - Dublin Core Elements. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

In addition to the default Dublin Core metadata, I will use the 'Person' item type which provides biographical elements, customising it by creating additional elements to reflect my dataset (Fig. 15). The three elements to be added are: 'Place of Association' and 'Writing Genre', which exist as fields in my dataset and are self-explanatory; the third custom element that I will add is 'Logainm Permanent Link' in order to attach geo-locational reference data to each item. These data are not in my dataset and will be input manually during a later stage in the workflow. I also change the display order, as above with DC elements.

Figure 15 - Person Item Type Metadata Fields. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

In total I identified 23 metadata elements for the dataset in Omeka. As the 15 DC elements are, with some exceptions, common to each of the writers I use a plugin ‘Default Dublin Core’ to populate these fields. It should be noted that all of these fields can be amended at a later stage, if required. This plugin enables the auto-population of Dublin Core fields with values that I have specified at time of item ingest/creation and is configured via the plugins/admin page of Omeka (figs. 16, 17). In order to decide on the default values I referred to a similar dataset Irish Women at Work Oral History Project in DRI (*Digital Repository of Ireland*, n.d.), the print edition of the MWW Dictionary, and also relied on my own knowledge of both Dublin Core and metadata requirements.

Figure 16 - Omeka Plugin Set-up. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Default Coverage

Munster, Ireland, 1800-2000

Add or edit this Coverage entry. This will be added to the Dublin Core Coverage field automatically when a new or existing record is saved, but if and only if that field is empty. Consult <http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/tgn/index.html> for help with geographic names.

Default Creator

O'Toole, Tina

Add or edit this Creator entry. This will be added to the Dublin Core Creator field automatically when a new or existing record is saved, but if and only if that field is empty.

Default Date

1800-2000

Add or edit this Date entry. This will be added to the Dublin Core Date field automatically when a new or existing record is saved, but if and only if that field is empty. Consult <https://www.w3.org/TR/NOTE-datetime> for help with standard date formats.

Default Description

Bibliographic Dictionary Entry

Add or edit this Description entry. This will be added to the Dublin Core Description field automatically when a new or existing record is saved, but if and only if that field is empty.

Default Format

Text

Add or edit this Format entry. This will be added to the Dublin Core Format field automatically when a new or existing record is saved, but if and only if that field is empty. Consult <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml> for help with media types.

Figure 17 - Default Dublin Core Settings. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

For the remaining eight elements which form the ‘Person’ item-type I undertook a data-mapping exercise with my master Tipperary writers spreadsheet, reducing the 49 fields to eight. See Appendix D - Omeka Mapping, for complete details of the data mapping, field descriptions and values.

I saved my new dataset as [**filename: MWW_TippOnly_Mapped.csv**]

Data Import Process

Data can be entered into Omeka manually, or automatically as a batch import. Prior to data ingest I installed and configured two plugins to automate the process, ‘Default Dublin Core’ described above and ‘CSV Import’ (Fig. 18, 19) a plugin which enables the import of content (items) as a .csv file. The data needs to be formatted as part of this process using prescribed column headers in the following format: {Person}:{Place_Of_Association}. I created a new .csv file with my dataset using the appropriate headings (Table 3, below) matching the criteria for import.

Saved as [filename: MWW_TippOnly_Mapped_OmekaImport.csv]

Table 3 - CSV Import - Omeka Mapping

JM ID	Field Name	Description	CSV import plugin field
3	Extent_Of_Work	Dates associated with the writer	{Dublin Core}:{Coverage}
32	Place_Of_Birth	Place of birth of the writer	{Person}:{Birthplace}
33	Place_Of_Association	Place of association of the writer	{Person}:{Place_Of_Association}
40	Connective_Phrase2	All genres associated with writer	{Person}:{writing_genre}
46	Notes	Biographical Summary	{Person}:{Biographical Text}
49	Keywords	Name of writer	{Dublin Core}:{Title}

[Note: While attempting to run this operation I got multiple errors relating to the PHP path. Using the Omeka site resources I was able to identify the precise issue and rectify it. The error is described in Appendix E.]

Munster Women Writers Plugins Appearance Users Settings Welcome, Super User

CSV Import

Import Items Status

Step 1: Select File and Item Settings

Upload CSV File* Maximum file size is 150 MB.
 MWW_TippO...ekalimport.csv

Use an export from Omeka CSV Report Selecting this will override the options below.

Automap Column Names to Elements Automatically maps columns to elements based on their column names. The column name must be in the form: {ElementSetName}{ElementName}

Select Item Type
 Person

Select Collection
 Munster Women Writers

Make All Items Public?

Feature All Items?

Figure 18 - Omeka CSV Import, Step 1. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Figure 19 - Omeka CSV Import, Step 2. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Before reviewing the data that had been ingested, I installed the following plugins to provide additional functionality when undertaking this process. Appendix E provides further detailed information for all the plugins used for the creation of this artefact.

Bulk Metadata Editor

This plugin allows for global editing of records in the database.

Clickable Links Plus

This plugin allows for the creation of clickable hyperlinks in plaintext fields. I applied this to the *Logainm* Permanent Link field and the Relation field.

The Omeka resource has been successfully populated using the information from the Tipperary writers dataset. The database holds 61 records. At this stage I undertook a review of all the entries, making corrections where necessary. At the end of this process I have now achieved Objective 1 - to (re)present data gathered by the MWW project.

4.5 Workflow Stage 3 - Enhancing Omeka

One of the strengths of Omeka is the ability to enhance the core archive and preservation data by presenting the data through different lenses, expanding and challenging our understanding of the dataset, and prompting new ways of thinking about the data. Omeka also offers the ability to create collections and exhibits, grouping items thematically and, using a plugin called ‘Simple Pages’, additional information can be provided to add value to the objects in the core dataset.

Overall Appearance

There are a number of themes available in Omeka by default, and it is also possible to create your own, although some knowledge of CSS and PHP is required for this. I selected the Seasons theme as it suited my text heavy dataset. Many aspects of the appearance, such as page navigation and hierarchies, default image sizes, and display settings are configurable from the Omeka Admin/Appearance page in the browser. All of these are easily configurable using the GUI via radio buttons.

Adding general information to the resource

The ‘Simple Pages’ plugin allows for the creation of basic web pages for the Omeka resource. I created a number of pages, providing background to both the original MWW project, and also to the proof-of-concept project. These pages are primarily text-based but can be written using html (my preferred option) and it is possible to include images, text, and hyperlinks (Fig. 20). Once the Simple Pages plugin has been installed pages are administered via the sidebar in the Omeka Admin view, where they can be ordered, and set as public or private. Omeka also supports shortcode functionality, allowing for the quick addition of embedded objects in many text fields.

Figure 20 - Simple Pages plugin, Short-code Example. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Fig. 21 below displays the same information as that shown in Fig. 20 above, but from the perspective of the end-user interface.

Figure 21 - Simple Pages GUI View. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Creating Collections

It is possible to divide the content in the database thematically, or by type, using Collection functionality. I began by creating a collection called Writers Database, to which I added the 61 writer items (Fig. 22). I then created a second collection called ‘Original Website Elements’. These two sets of items can be now viewed discretely as collections, but also as a single dataset, using the ‘Browse All Items’.

The screenshot shows the 'Collection Information Page' for 'Writer's Database'. The page is divided into two main sections: a metadata table on the left and a control panel on the right.

Title	Writer's Database
Description	<p>A bibliographic dictionary of women writers from or associated with Co Tipperary, covering the period 1800-2000.</p> <p>This represents a subset of data, gathered by the Munster Women Writers Project during its lifetime.</p> <p>All entries are as published on the original Munster Women Writers Project website 2007-2013.</p> <p>*Information has not been updated or corrected since original publication.*</p> <p>Project output was also made available in hard copy as print publication <i>Dictionary of Munster Women Writers, 1800-2000</i>, Tina O'Toole (editor), published in 2005 by Cork University Press.</p> <p>*Munster - a province in the geographical south of the Republic of Ireland. https://www.logainm.ie/1165971.aspx</p>
Date	1800-2000
Creator	O'Toole, Tina Munster Women Writers Project
Source	Munster Women Writers Project, University College Cork
Publisher	Women and Irish Society Project, University College Cork
Rights	 This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International License .
Coverage	Munster, Ireland, 1800-2000
Relation	Dictionary of Munster Women Writers, 1800-2000

Control Panel:

- [Edit](#) (green button)
- [View Public Page](#) (blue button)
- [Delete](#) (red button)

Public: Yes **Featured:** No

Total Number of Items: 61

Contributors:

- Dr Tina O'Toole, General Editor

Output Formats:

- [csv](#)
- [omeka-xml](#)

Figure 22 - Collection Information Page. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Adding Items

Using the Internet Archive’s WayBack Machine (*Internet Archive: Wayback Machine*, n.d.) I harvested screenshots from a 2013 instance of the original MWW website, and then add each as a new item. Using the Default Dublin Core plugin I was again able to pre-populate values for the items. I also used the item type ‘Still Image’, rather than ‘Person’ for additional metadata values. I attached the image file to each record, a relatively straightforward process. I also add items (primarily .gif) from the original .rar package provided by Jonathan Neville; and other documents that I consider useful (Fig. 23).

Collection Items

MWW Project Logo
Project logo, as used on poster, website, publications

Towards a Feminist Literary History Conference Poster 1
MWW Conference Poster, July 20-22, 2001.
Venue: University College, Cork

Towards a Feminist Literary History Conference Poster 2
MWW Conference Poster, July 20-22, 2001.
Venue: University College, Cork
With list of speakers and contact details.

Figure 23 - Collection Elements Page. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Munster Women Writers Project

About ▾ Browse Collections Browse All Items Map of Writers Map Views Browse Exhibits

Pilot Project Background
Original Project Background
Digital Humanities in Ireland
Project Resources

ITEMS (3 TOTAL) Sort by: Title Date Added ▲

Writer's Database
A bibliographic dictionary of women writers from or associated with Co Tipperary, covering the period 1800-2000. This represents a subset of data,...

Contributors: Dr Tina O'Toole, General Editor
View the items in Writer's Database

Original Website Elements
Images and text from the original website of the Munster Women Writers Project which was live from 2007-2013. The website took the form of a...

Contributors: Murphy, Joan, O'Toole, Tina
View the items in Original Website Elements

Figure 24 – 'About' Sub-menu Items. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

I have now achieved Objective 2 - To provide a brief history of the MWW project, images from the original project website, and an overview of the processes undertaken in this case study.

4.6 Workflow Stage 4 - Interoperability

The third objective of using Omeka is to ensure that the artefact created is a resource that complies with best practice for data management, adhering to FAIR Principles and Open Access objectives, it achieves this by way of interoperability, facilitated by metadata standards and Open Source functionality. The addition of a number of plugins greatly enhances Omeka's interoperability, and the following plugins are added for this purpose.

Clickable Links Plus

This plugin allows for the creation of clickable hyperlinks in plaintext fields. I applied this to the *Logainm* Permanent Link field and the Relation field. Although not specifically related to interoperability this plugin enables the end-user to go directly to related resources, which open in a new window.

COinS

This plugin allows for the embedding of bibliographic metadata in the html address of the item page, enabling the end-user to employ tools such as Zotero.

CSV Export Format

This allows users to export records and search results etc., as a .csv file.

OAI-PMH Repository

This plugin exposes Omeka items to repository harvesters, allowing the Dublin Core metadata to be accessed by data aggregators.

I have achieved Objective 3 - To present a Dublin Core compliant resource that is searchable using OAI protocols and suitable for web archiving, and aggregation by DRI/Europeana. For a complete list of plugins used for the customisation of this Omeka installation see Appendix E - Omeka Technical and Plugins.

4.7 Workflow Stage 5 - Adding Maps and Timelines

In this section I will give an overview of alternative ways that the knowledge collected by the MWW project can be represented. Two approaches that I wanted to pursue included different visual representations of the data, using maps and timelines, both possible using plugins, and the application of tags would allow for the data to be accessed by sub-topic.

At the same time as I reviewed the metadata for each of the writer entries, I also added information to the Tags field (more correctly known as keywords) to indicate the writing genres, places of association etc. These tags are searchable and the database can be browsed using them, providing an additional entry route to the dataset (Fig. 25).

Figure 25 - 'Browse Tags' Edit Page. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Maps and Timelines using Built-in Functionality

As described previously (Section 4.4) the batch ingest of 61 writers to Omeka populated a number of fields automatically, both Dublin Core and item-type metadata. All of these fields are searchable. It is also possible to add further information and resources using the standard Add/Edit Item interface namely: Files, Tags and Map data. While I have not attached files to any of the Writers Database Collection it is something that can be done at a later stage; for items associated with the Original Website Collection I have added .gif and .png files as appropriate.

Omeka allows for the association of a location with an item using its own Geolocation plugin. The settings are configured globally using the Admin tool, and it is here that I was able to choose from a selection of Open Source base maps (I selected OpenStreetMap as the default) and set coordinates for the centre point for my map and the default zoom level (Fig. 26).

Figure 26 - Map view and Settings. (Source: Omeka Screenshots)

Two important visual considerations here were: the number of locations that I wanted to appear on the map view when browsing, which I set to a figure higher than the number of entries in the database, as I wanted to ensure that all would be visible simultaneously; and the ability to view locations as clusters (depending on the zoom level), a tool that I think is useful for presenting a visual sense of where writers were/are concentrated (note the yellow Clonmel cluster in map above).

At Add/Edit Item level, it is possible to add the location by searching the map (Fig. 27) and also, in cases where the location name is not recognised by the underlying Geocoder, by dropping a pin.

Figure 27 - Edit Item - Set Location. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

There are some disadvantages to the built-in map browser, both a consequence of it using a single latitude/longitude coordinate. The first issue is that it is only possible to associate a single geographical location with each writer, meaning that for some entries I had to decide between Place of Birth and Place of Association. The second issue is that for writers where no detailed information (below county level) was available I was unable to add any location. I addressed this challenge by creating a custom field ‘*Logainm* Permanent Link’ where I could enter a link to *Logainm* (Placenames Database of Ireland, n.d.). *Logainm* references are displayed as hyperlinks in the item metadata and (where known) have been provided for each writer at as detailed a level as possible (Fig. 28). As the *Logainm* data is available as a polygon (i.e., a bounded area) it differs from the latitude/longitude coordinates available using the built-in Omeka mapping tool. The link launches the *Logainm* website in a new window. As can be seen from the screenshot it is possible to get down to a very fine level of granularity using the *Logainm* dataset.

The screenshot displays the Logainm website interface for the entry 'Tipperary'. On the left, there are three filter sections:

- Sort by:** 'Irish name' (checked) and 'English name'.
- Filter by county:** 'no filter' (10), 'Tipperary' (9), and 'Cork' (1).
- Filter by category:** 'no filter' (10), 'electoral division' (3), 'administrative county' (2), 'minor feature' (1), 'civil parish' (1), 'town' (1), 'townland' (1), and 'county' (1).

The main content area shows three entries for 'Tiobraid Árann/Tipperary':

- Civil parish:** Includes a map of the parish and a 'More' button. Metadata: COUNTY: Tiobraid Árann/Tipperary, BARONY: Clann Liam/Clanwilliam.
- County:** Includes a map of the county and a 'More' button. Metadata: county.
- Town:** Includes a map of the town and a 'More' button. Metadata: COUNTY: Tiobraid Árann/Tipperary, BARONY: Clann Liam/Clanwilliam.

Figure 28 - Logainm Entry for Tipperary. (Source: <https://www.logainm.ie/en/s?txt=tipperary>)

Timelines

While Omeka does not have any built-in timeline functionality it is possible to embed a resource, such as a timeline created using the KnightLab (*KnightLab Timeline JS*, n.d.) tool, within a simple page, which is something that I have done (Fig. 29). However the timeline is not dynamic, as it is not linked to the underlying Omeka dataset, relying as it does on Google Spreadsheet resources.

Figure 29 - KnightLab Timeline. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

This led me to exploring another mapping and timeline option, the Neatline plugin suite (*Neatline*, n.d.).

Maps and Timelines using Neatline

Neatline offers a number of plugins for Omeka which work in combination to allow for the creation of maps and timelines (referred to as 'exhibits' by Neatline). I installed six Neatline plugins (see Appendix E for full list). The key functionality that I required was the ability to be able to view locational data on the map for each writer, and I wanted to be able to click on the writer and see biographical information.

Creating a Neatline map involved setting up a new exhibit. The first step of the process allowed me to select the base map, as with the Omeka built-in tool; however, I was also able to choose a static image or a custom WMS (Web Map Service) layer. Using an open source geo-rectifier (*Map Warper*, n.d.) I found a map of Tipperary (1901, map of civil parishes and boundaries) and created the exhibit (Fig. 30). The next step was to link the data from Omeka to the Neatline plugin. This link provides for a dynamic exchange between the Omeka dataset and the Neatline views so any updating of items in Omeka is reflected in the Neatline map. The process of importing the data for

display on the map was a straightforward import option on the Admin settings page (I selected the Writers dataset) but it should be noted that any items added to the collection after the initial import will need to be imported separately (i.e. the link is dynamic only once the items are present in the Neatline dataset).

Figure 30 - Neatline Map Using Mapwarper Base Layer. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Although all of the items were now available to Neatline, it was a laborious process to assign locations and dates to each for display on the map. The only field that auto-populated from the Omeka import was Title (which was the writer's name), so I had to add any other information manually. The 'Text' tab (Fig. 31) allowed me to add the item name to slug and biographical information to the body. 'Map' allowed me to add geolocational data, using a selection of 'Drawing Tools' (Fig. 31). Although I had already input location data in Omeka it was not possible to import this to a similar field in Neatline, which was frustrating, and as the Neatline tool contained no search function for this field I had to scroll and zoom in/out on the map to find locations that matched that in Omeka. In addition it was not possible to import the *Logainm* spatial data directly to Neatline as there were no import/export formats in common.

Figure 31 - Neatline Edit Views: Description and Spatial Data. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

the map which, when clicked on, showed the writer's name and biographical information. While the format/style for these pins is configurable individually, Neatline provides stylesheets functionality for this design element (using a 'dialect of CSS', (*Neatline Stylesheets*, n.d.)) at the collection level, so it is possible to assign values across all items in this way.

The resulting output (Fig. 32) provides a visualisation that allows access to the underlying data in a number of ways. Each writer is visible as a purple circle on the map. I opted not to assign labels to these circles for aesthetic reasons as the appearance was too cluttered. I have provided additional functionality by embedding a link in the descriptive text for the exhibit to allow for it to be viewed in full screen mode - a function available at admin level but not for the public user.

Figure 32 - Neatline End-user Map View. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

By using the A-Z list on the right of the map the user can select the writer and the corresponding circle will change to red. The writer’s names are also presented along the timeline, at the bottom of the map. By clicking on the name in either place, or by clicking on the circle itself, the biographical data is made visible on a pop-up (Fig. 33). The user can then scroll down through the biographical information to view more detailed information from the Omeka record and can also opt to see the entry in Omeka itself, exiting the Neatline map view.

Figure 33 - Neatline End-user Map View. Eliza Dalton Entry. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

4.8 Conclusion

In this chapter I have documented the tools, processes and workflows required to create a digital artefact, using a subset of data from the MWW project and making it available in digital form for the first time in almost a decade. The artefact has been designed in line with FAIR Principles, Open Data guidelines and sector best practices and this proof-of-concept has been delivered using open-source and freely available resources such as Omeka, Neatline and Open Refine. These tools do not require any great technical expertise or financial outlay, and as such offer low-barrier access to achieving sustainable practices in for digital Humanities projects.

The chapter has provided a detailed description of the processes undertaken, to offer practical guidance and insight. Of particular value are the screenshots which serve to illustrate challenges and issues, but also position this artefact creation in the specific digital environment accessible to those in the Irish education sector in 2022.

5. Findings

5.1 Introduction

The following chapter will analyse the artefact design and implementation process and consider how it aligns with the goals of digital sustainability. The structure will follow that of the previous chapter (Chapter 4 - Design and Implementation) and discuss findings with reference to the requirements identified at the outset (3.4 - Tools and System Requirements). Above all it will consider how the Omeka solution proposed matches Edmond and Morselli's understanding of sustainability as one which ensures that resources are 'optimised for reuse' (Edmond and Morselli, 2020, p.1029).

5.2 Data Preparation

Omeka supports knowledge representation in many different ways using maps, timelines, exhibits and collections, and the ability to manage rich metadata. Using the metadata standard Dublin Core (DC) is central to its functionality, as it provides an underlying structure that facilitates search, retrieval, display and dissemination (as well as interoperability).

There was no data dictionary available to me at the start of this process which meant that considerable time was spent in trying to establish the meaning for each of the 49 fields in the original dataset. Some were self-explanatory (Journal_Title_Without_The), some seemed self-explanatory (Title_Analytic), others were abstract (Medium_Designator2). After creating the data dictionary, I was then required to do a mapping to the Dublin Core element set, and Person item-type. The limited number of elements in the DC dataset is both a strength and a weakness. On the plus side it provides logical terms, expressed in plain language, and the Dublin Core website (DCMI, n.d.) offers robust descriptive information alongside clear examples. On the negative side it is a basic set of elements, which lacks the richness of schemas such as EADS, MODS or MARC21. Inevitably, when reducing the number of fields from 49 to 15 some data loss occurred.

I had initially thought that the data cleansing process would not begin until I had created my subset of Tipperary writers, however the errors, formatting issues, anomalies and Irish language place

names required that I begin the task much earlier in the process than I had hoped. The dataset did not immediately offer a clear link between bibliographic rows and biographical information, and it was only after spending some time that I found a way to link the two (via a workaround using the Keywords field). It was in this way that I was able to extract just the biographical information. I then had to examine it line by line to find the Tipperary entries, as the relevant information could appear in one of three different fields, and in either Irish or English. As a by-product of this effort, I created a version of the master dataset which indicates the place of association for all c.560 writers.

The dataset included both Irish- and English-language content, which posed two challenges. The first was the technical issues that arose with corruption of *fadas* between file formats (an all-too-common issue which arises due to use of ASCII rather than Unicode, that is outside the scope of this dissertation). This dictated that I proceed using .csv and the legacy .xls file format. The second challenge was around the issue of translation, when and where was it appropriate to translate. As I am not fluent in the Irish language I made the following decisions, which a native speaker may not have made.

1. All Irish-language entries were input verbatim. As I am unfamiliar with Irish I was unable to undertake even a cursory review of the content.
2. When adding genres (customised for the Person item-type) I provided both the original term (in Irish) and an English translation. I did not do this in reverse for the English language entries.
3. When adding placenames I provided both the original term (in Irish) and an English translation. I did not do this in reverse for the English language entries.

5.3 Creating Omeka Resource

Omeka is an object-oriented relational database, the central concept being of an entity, with associated attributes. The dataset for this proof-of-concept is fundamentally a dictionary, and the biographical nature of the resource lends itself to the object-oriented repository, with the core entity being the individual writer. Omeka refers to this core entity/object as an ‘item’. The ability to automate parts of the item creation process using plugins saved a significant amount of time,

and also meant that the level of accuracy was consistent across items. While the data preparation was time-consuming in itself once the task was completed the item creation was instant upon ingest. The ability to add custom fields (elements) to the existing item-types was also hugely beneficial, with over half of the fields pre-populated.

Once the information was presented back to me in Omeka I realised there were a few fields that I had populated incorrectly at ingest. This only became apparent to me once I had entered the items and done some testing (searches, exports, visualisations) on the dataset. For example, initially I had set the DC Publisher field to MWW, rather than the overall WISP/UCC project, which required a global edit to change. Correcting these mistakes was straightforward as the admin tools in Omeka are user-friendly and require little expertise to master, but the process does take time. The Bulk Metadata Editor plugin provided powerful functionality which helped.

As a proof-of-concept it worked well, but I did need to edit/amend each record individually, and for future projects I would propose ingesting a smaller subset of data initially, appraising its appearance in Omeka and then spending additional time at the data preparation phase, to reduce the amount of time spent editing in Omeka after items are created.

Using the Default Dublin Core plugin meant that the Omeka resource was immediately available in a format suitable for export or aggregation by other repositories, a significant advantage in terms of my digital sustainability goals.

5.4 Enhancing Omeka

A clean Omeka instance provides sufficient functionality to meet the basic goal of creating a Dublin Core-compliant resource, but it is by the addition of plugins that it can be made even more open and accessible.

Clickable Links Plus allowed me to add hyperlinks to non-HTML fields, which I found useful for the default DC Relation and a customised location field. While I didn't populate the Relation field for most of the entries I suggest that it could be useful at a later stage of the project, linking end-users to other authoritative sources such as entries in the Dictionary of Irish Biography (*DIB*, n.d.)

or (possibly less authoritatively) Wikipedia. By using it in the *Logainm* Permanent Link field it allows the user to go straight to the national place names database. Both fields were populated manually, after the items had been created but, if time allowed, they could have been added to the original .csv import file. See Iota, Temple Lane and Molly Keane for examples of entries with links to both DIB and *Logainm*.

Creating Collections and Exhibits allowed me to present the data in different ways, making it easier to meet a broader range of end-user needs. Although I did not explore the Exhibits function in any great detail it allowed me to gather material from different collections and add descriptive content pages. The facility to embed images, videos, timelines was particularly useful and it was here that I was able to include timelines made using Knight Lab tools. These timelines did not offer a dynamic link to the Omeka resources but did provide an alternative ‘view’ of the data.

5.5 Interoperability

The COinS and OAI-PMH plugins were simple to add and required no further intervention from me to implement their functionality. In order to validate the site as OAI compliant (Fig. 34) I used the Open Archives Initiative validation tool (*OAI-PMH*, n.d.) and the site has also been registered with them as a repository.

The screenshot displays the OAI-PMH Validator tool interface. At the top, the logo for 'OAI PMH validator' is shown alongside the text 'Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) Validator & data extractor Tool'. Below this, a navigation bar includes options like 'Validate URL', 'Validate By Direct Input', 'Download XML', and 'REST API'. The main input area shows the OAI-PMH URL: 'https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/oai-pmh-repository/request', with a 'Check now >' button. Below the input, a list of available commands is shown on the left, with 'ListSets' selected. The main content area displays the results of a 'ListSets Validation' (8 items), including: '1. HTTP status 200', '2. Content type text/xml;charset=UTF-8', '3. Content XML checked.', '4. Request time is 0.64 sec', '5. XML complies with OAI-PMH XML Schema http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/OAI-PMH.xsd', '6. Found set "MWW Project Resources" with setSpec "2".', '7. Found set "Tipperary Writers Database" with setSpec "3".', and '8. Found set "MWW Original Website Elements" with setSpec "4".' An 'XML Result' of 2 KB is also indicated.

Figure 34 - OAI-PMH Validation. (Source: Author Screenshot)

In addition to the standard export formats (atom, dcme-xml, iso, omeka-xml and rss2) I was able to add .csv export functionality also (Fig. 35).

Figure 35 - Omeka Output Formats. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

All of these tools make the dataset more visible and accessible, meeting more of my sustainability goals.

One of the objectives of the pilot project was to create a resource that was suitable for web archiving as WARC files. In order to confirm that this had been achieved I used *WARCreate* (Kelly, 2022) a browser plugin to harvest sample pages from the site as WARC files, and then used Open Source tools provided by Webrecorder (*Webrecorder*, n.d.) to view and validate the WARC files that had been created (Fig. 36).

Figure 36 - Validation of WARC Files Using Replay. (Source: Author Screenshot)

In addition to the above the resource has also been saved to the Internet Archive (Fig. 37) as:
<https://web.archive.org/web/20220805115257/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/>

INTERNET ARCHIVE

WayBackMachine

[DONATE](#)

Saving page

http://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com

✓ Done! 👤 First Archive

A snapshot was captured. Visit page:
</web/20220805115257/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/>

https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/
https://ajax.googleapis.com/ajax/libs/jqueryui/1.12.1/jquery-ui.min.js
https://ajax.googleapis.com/ajax/libs/jquery/3.6.0/jquery.min.js
https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/plugins/Geolocation/views/shared/javascripts/leaflet/leaflet.css?v=3.2.2
https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/plugins/Geolocation/views/shared/css/geolocation-marker.css?v=3.2.2
https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/plugins/Geolocation/views/shared/javascripts/leaflet-markercluster/MarkerCluster.Default.css?v=3.2.2
https://fonts.googleapis.com/css?

If something goes wrong please click [here](#) to send us an error report. Downloaded elements: 33

Saving outlinks and their embedded resources

</web/20220805115355/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/digital-humanities-in-ireland> ✓ Done! 👤 First Archive

</web/20220805115322/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/original-project-background> ✓ Done! 👤 First Archive

</web/20220805115326/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/geolocation/map/browse> ✓ Done! 👤 First Archive

</web/20220805115342/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/pilot-project-background> ✓ Done! 👤 First Archive

</web/20220805115320/https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/tech-resources>

Figure 37 - Archived Instance on Internet Archive. (Source: Author Screenshot)

5.6 Maps and Timelines

Maps and timelines allow for different perspectives on a dataset which in turn allows for different interpretations of the underlying data. Connections that require painstaking effort to determine from a spreadsheet can become immediately obvious when that data is represented on a map or timeline. A case in point is the yellow ‘Clonmel Cluster’ (Fig. 38).

Figure 38 - Clonmel Cluster, Omeka Map View. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Creating maps using Omeka was not as straightforward as it could have been. Both approaches that I tried required editing/amending an item once it was created; there was no way to auto-populate the field. Neither Neatline nor Geolocation could deal with the varying levels of granularity for the location data that I had, or with the multiple locations for some items. The most elegant solution would have been the ability to add polygon data. This was not an option using Geolocation plugin but would have been possible in Neatline if I had been able to provide the *Logainm* data in Well-Known Text (WKT) format. Unfortunately I was unable to find a way to convert the various export formats offered by *Logainm* (RDF JSON, RDF XML) to WKT.

I think the workaround that I used, creating a specific field with a link to the *Logainm* dataset, will be useful at some future point, and it is entirely feasible that a plugin could be developed to automate this process by allowing the polygon values in the underlying database.

The integration between Neatline and Omeka is not seamless; items must be imported initially from Omeka, before map and timeline functionality can be added. In addition, the import process

must be repeated for any additional entries, which is a step that could be easily overlooked if adding a large collection of items over time. Once in Neatline the items are dynamically updated from Omeka and unlike Geolocation the NeatlineFeatures mapping tool provides a highly customisable visual solution using style sheets, requiring a basic understanding of CSS and HTML.

Standalone Neatline timeline functionality didn't work for me, but I was able to present the information as part of the map. Overall, I thought this provided too much information in one place - the timeline appears along the bottom of the map - but I was able to remove spans and just provide DOB information, which removed some of the clutter. The embedded Knight Lab timelines using Exhibits functionality were much more aesthetically appealing, although as they link to a version of the data hosted by a third party (Google) they are not dynamic and require additional effort to maintain. The images were all sourced via Wikimedia Commons, in line with my Open requirements.

5.7 Incomplete Records Summary

The primary data-set included errors, formatting issues and anomalies. For the most common issues I used Table 4 as a guide.

Table 4 - Incomplete Records Summary

Issue	Steps taken	Consequence	Design Decision
Entries listed generic 'Tipperary' in place of birth or association	Did not create a geo-locational entry for the writer	Not visible on map (6 of 61 writers)	Provide link in <i>Logainm</i> field at county level
Entries with more than one location	Undertook additional research, selected a single location, based on 'best guess'	Visible on map, but possibly inaccurate	Provide link to both locations in <i>Logainm</i> field
Entries had no birth or death dates, or listed as 'contemporary'	Undertook additional research. Dates entered at item level.	If birth value unknown, set default to 1950	Only birth dates made visible on timeline
Genres and place names listed in Irish language	Translated to English	Duplication of effort	Provide information in both languages

5.8 General Considerations

Omeka provides a good level of customisation in terms of appearance and functionality, whilst also adhering to clear metadata standards and structures. As an Open Source application, the code (PHP) is configurable for each instance and APIs can be developed to suit particular requirements. Customisation can be achieved at a number of levels, such as simply changing themes using check boxes, and Omeka offers many useful options for those who are unfamiliar with CMSs. The barriers for access are low, both for administrators and end-users.

In terms of sustainability there are some concerns about the potential obsolescence of plugins. This manifests itself in two ways - for those plugins that are being maintained there is a risk that as new versions are released functionality may break for those using older versions. Most worrying of all is the situation with third parties who have previously contributed significant functionality but who are now unable to continue supporting the tools provided (see 'Neatline's Current Status' post, *What is Neatline?*, n.d.).

Omeka offers a Dublin Core-based metadata schema which is customisable allowing for the addition of rich metadata. It supports OAI-PMH for Open Access discoverability and website harvesting. It offers excellent advanced search functionality to facilitate research, and content can be exported in a variety of commonly used formats. Knowledge can be represented in a variety of ways such as maps and timelines, as well as structured lists.

It is user-friendly and highly customisable with a low barrier to entry in terms of engagement and access, for both administrators and end-users. It has an active user base and support structure and is widely used in the GLAM and education sector, where it is considered to be a robust and reliable tool. Supporting interoperability with tools such as Zotero and adhering to industry best practice metadata standards, it is an Open Source application which is highly extensible and has an active API development community.

5.9 Conclusion

It is clear that achieving sustainability, particularly for small digital Humanities projects and digital collections, requires continuous effort. Planning for the sustainability challenges of access, visibility, interoperability and maintainability should always be considered from the outset.

Edmond and Morselli (2020) argue that sustainability should be understood as ‘optimised for reuse’ (p.1029), which my findings show is possible using Omeka. It is a CMS tool with a user-friendly admin GUI, which addresses issues of access barriers to researchers such as limited technical expertise and financial resources. It also proposes an approach which allows individual projects to make design decisions at a local level, whilst staying within the framework of Dublin Core metadata standards and open access requirements such as OAI compatibility. It provides a solution for knowledge representation and dissemination facilitating access to digital content in a researcher-friendly manner.

While it does not address high level issues such as infrastructure and policy it does provide significant affordances for availability, access, longevity and interoperability of Humanities data; as a solution for legacy projects, it presents an excellent way-point *en route* to a national digital repository of the future.

6. Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to provide a review of this dissertation and the research undertaken for it. It will begin by re-stating the research problem and giving an overview of the research objectives. It will then place this dissertation within the Body of Knowledge by summarising the findings of the questions posed in order to address the objectives. The chapter will go on to discuss the limitations of the research and will conclude with recommendations for future work and research.

The dissertation was divided into six chapters, with appendices, and was accompanied by a digital artefact. Details of the digital output can be found in the Digital Manifest. A summary of the content of each chapter is provided below.

Chapter One gave an introduction to the research topic and presented the research objectives, methodologies, resources, scope and limitations.

Chapter Two provided a review of the literature on the topic of sustainability in the digital Humanities, considering the epistemological issue of the term. It situated the sustainability challenges in an Irish context, presenting a view of the landscape for digital Humanities in Ireland.

Chapter Three outlined the epistemology, methodology and methods to be used to address the research question: a Literature Review, and a case study incorporating Restoration and Repurposing to create a digital artefact.

Chapter Four documented the design and implementation process. It presented a detailed review of the processes under six section headings: Data Acquisition, Data Preparation, Creating an Omeka Resource, Enhancing Functionality, Interoperability and Plugins, and Adding Maps and Timelines.

Chapter Five addressed the research objectives by providing an analysis of the digital artefact design and implementation. It evaluated the major findings within the context of the sustainability issues identified in the Literature Review.

Chapter Six reflects on the dissertation process and its outputs, and makes suggestions for future work.

The appendices include extensive detail on the Irish digital Humanities landscape by way of diagrams and tables. They also offer supporting material for the creation of the digital artefact. Most importantly, in Appendix B, a guide for those undertaking similar projects is presented.

6.2 Research Definition

The research problem that this dissertation addressed was the challenge of sustainability for digital projects in the Humanities in Ireland, which was identified as a gap in the literature (Davis, 2019; Estill, 2019; Su and Zhang, 2022). The objectives designed to address the problem were:

- 1 Identify challenges for sustainability of Irish digital Humanities projects
- 2 Offer a practical approach to meet sustainability challenges

It was proposed that the objectives could be met by way of a literature review and the creation of a digital artefact. A case study of the Munster Women Writers website *munsterwomen.ie* was identified as an apposite example of a ‘lost’ project that could be returned to the digital realm by way of a proof-of-concept website.

The scope was clearly established in Chapter 1, situating the dissertation within the field of digital projects in the Humanities, which the author described as ‘digital Humanities’ noting the lower case ‘D’. It sought to offer a practical solution for those facing the challenge of ensuring sustainability for digital projects by recovering a ‘lost’ digital project and demonstrating what is achievable in 2022, using tools, technologies and techniques aligned with the Open movement.

6.3 Contribution to the Body of Knowledge

This section represents the contribution to the Body of Knowledge, Section 6.3.1 will focus on the first research objective: *Identify challenges for sustainability of Irish digital Humanities projects*. Section 6.3.2 will focus on the second objective: *Offer a practical approach to meet sustainability challenges*.

6.3.1 Challenges for sustainability of Irish digital Humanities project

Five questions were proposed to address this research objective. This section will provide a summary of the findings for all. The findings, accompanied by observations from the author, represent the contribution to the Body of Knowledge.

1. What constitutes a digital Humanities project?

This question sought to present a clearer understanding of the term ‘digital Humanities project’ and following a brief consideration of the discrete academic discipline of Digital Humanities as one that still evades precise definition (Murphy *et al.*, 2020) it proposed that the term be understood broadly as encompassing the use of digital tools and methodologies in the Humanities field (Edmond, 2016; McGinnis, 2019). The author concurs with Drucker’s assertion that ‘we need to think of the work of digital humanities as radically incomplete, always ongoing’ (2021, p.93). The discipline of the Humanities has undergone, and is still undergoing, a paradigm shift as digital technologies disrupt the centuries-old structures of the Academy. The Digital Humanities has been at the forefront of this sometimes traumatic shift. Borrowing from the discipline of Psychology, itself no stranger to epistemological crisis within the Academy (Teo, 2017), I would add to Drucker’s notion of the ‘radically incomplete’ by proposing that Radical Acceptance (Linehan, 1993) should now be employed by scholars in the field. After almost 30 years of argument and discussion about the place of technology in the Humanities, it is time for the energy of debate to turn its focus away from division and definition and toward inclusivity and integration. The ‘ivory tower’ forces holding out against the use of technologies in the ‘traditional’ Humanities use the lack of codification as a way of dismissing and undermining digital outputs. By putting infrastructures in place to support the sustainability of such output, this argument against technology in the Humanities can be negated. Radical Acceptance is required if the Humanities

are to survive in an age of technological innovation. As Hall (2012) says ‘Accepting doesn’t mean agreeing...it’s exhausting to fight reality, and it doesn't work’.

2. What are the key concepts and issues relating to sustainability in digital projects in the Humanities?

The purpose of this question was to give the reader a grounding in the concepts and issues relating to sustainability, which the literature review found to be a complex issue with Drucker describing the intellectual considerations of sustainability in the context of knowledge production as a ‘complex epistemological object’ (2021, p.xx91). The environmental impacts of digital technologies and efforts to address them in the context of digital humanities (DHCC, 2022) were considered outside the scope of this research and the author chose to focus on Edmond and Morselli’s definition of sustainability as ‘optimised for reuse’ (2020, p.1029). With this definition in mind the review of the literature identified the key challenges to sustainability presented in terms of access, availability, longevity, funding and policy/vision (Dombrowski, 2014; Beneš *et al.*, 2016; Eschenfelder *et al.*, 2019; Kálmán *et al.*, 2019).

3. How did contemporaneous projects achieve sustainability?

A brief examination of the literature looked at three contemporaneous projects in the same area as the MWW project. Often cited as exemplars (Wernimont, 2013) both Brown University’s Women Writers Project (*Women Writers Online*, n.d.) and the Orlando project (*Orlando*, n.d.) have been maintained over the past twenty years and are still available. Orlando, in particular, is still being developed and has recently been relaunched as Orlando 2.0, now using Linked Open Data. Crucially both projects were collaborative endeavours from their genesis, involving technologists and computer scientists and using semantic tools and structures to scaffold their resources. However neither could be considered to be ‘accessible’ as they both reside behind paywalls. This research does not propose to address the reasons why *munsterwomen.ie* became a ‘lost’ digital project but it is clear from comparison with both *Orlando* and *Women Writers Online* that sustainability requires an interdisciplinary and collaborative approach, strong institutional support (and funding), robust project management and a clear, unified project vision (Woods, 1994; Brown *et al.*, 2007; Ballaster *et al.*, 2019).

4. What efforts are being made for similar ‘lost’ digital endeavours?

The purpose of this question was to establish current thoughts on best practice in the recovery of legacy projects, but little was found in the literature on the topic. The LIS domain provided most of the material as professionals in the Library Sciences find themselves at the forefront of stewardship of digital resources, with Sweeney *et al.* (2017) asserting that both the academic and library communities have a shared responsibility for sustainability. Smithies *et al.* (2019) make a distinction between digital outputs that require ongoing maintenance (intellectual/technical) and those that can be safely archived for the record. Their review concludes that the key to creating sustainability is a robust Software Development Lifecycle process: a process which ensures visibility of sustainability issues from the point of project conception. While Antonin *et al.* (2020) suggested two approaches to project recovery Restoration and Repurposing, there was a marked absence in the literature of practical examples for the recovery of similar ‘lost’ digital projects.

5. What are the sustainability challenges in an Irish context?

This question sought to interrogate sustainability challenges through the lens of infrastructures situating the issues within the Irish context. The literature review identified an absence of national strategy for the digital Humanities in Ireland. It showed the research landscape to be a disparate one and outlined the silo-based nature of repositories. It highlighted the lack of a national infrastructure as an obstacle to interoperability and Open Access requirements. Of particular note was the lack of Humanities scholars’ involvement in recent initiatives such as those by NORF and HEAnet, and the absence of an advocacy group at national level to represent the needs of Humanities scholars producing digital content. My personal observations on these findings are presented below.

I. The Academy

The lack of buy-in from the academic community has been identified as a key challenge to sustainability (Dombrowski, 2014; Drucker, 2021) and despite the efforts of dedicated individuals, many working in the Irish Humanities are struggling to engage with the changes that the use of technology brings. Of particular concern is the impact of changes in digital publishing. While professional progression within Humanities discipline remains tied to the monograph as the measure of success for promotion and recognition, scholars will not be inclined to move away from that model. It will be the demands of funders that will ultimately drive change in this area, as FAIR and Open Access requirements impact and dictate the format(s) of research output.

However, until the Academy provides reward and recognition for the efforts of non-monograph output by making changes to the metrics by which research is judged, scholars will continue to find themselves in a catch-22 situation.

II. Advocacy Alliances

The importance of adherence to standards and protocols is best communicated by demonstrating the benefits to the wider academic community that their implementation brings. This needs to be communicated clearly, via peer networks, placing the needs of the Humanities scholar at the centre of the conversation. This should be seen as an ongoing process, one requiring multiple iterations, in order for sustainability concepts to become embedded in the research process. Research in the Humanities is multi-faceted, relying as much on the individual research projects as on collaborative group endeavours. This disparate group of scholars has differing needs and the support by peer organisations should acknowledge this, while offering practical advice, guidelines and training around digital sustainability issues. The UK-IRL DHN is currently engaged in research and consultation with a view to establishing a permanent DH association for Ireland & the UK and has already demonstrated a clear need for such a group through its workshop output.

III. National Strategy and Infrastructure

In the absence of a national strategy the needs of Humanities scholars will not be addressed, and, as stated above the development of a national strategy depend largely on the support of advocacy groups, which are also absent from the Irish landscape. A national repository would ensure sustainability by offering the benefits of a TDR - individual repositories have neither the capacity, nor the finances, to allow them to mint persistent DOIs, or provide triple stores for their data. A number of national conversations are taking place at time of writing and the UK-IRL DHN offers some hope that Irish Humanities scholars may soon be represented at a national level. Although NORF's draft National Action Plan mentions the Humanities only once (in the context of FAIR research data) and has yet to involve the academic community in any meaningful way, it is to be hoped that this aspect of the forum will be developed over time. The DRI is ideally placed to drive this national strategy: it administers NORF and has had significant involvement with the development of FAIR Data Principles and it represents Ireland on expert groups such DARIAH-EU, RDA, ALLEA and Europeana to name but a few. Most importantly, the DRI is embedded in the Royal Irish Academy, the very heart of Ireland's Academic establishment. A national strategy

driven by DRI, backed by the RIA and sustained by infrastructures, including a national repository, would see Irish Humanities scholars well placed for the challenges to come.

6.3.2 Practical steps to address the sustainability challenge

The final question posed to address the research objective proposed a practical approach. A proof-of-concept digital artefact was created, using the *munsterwomen.ie* website of the MWW project as a case study to provide concrete examples of how digital sustainability could be achieved. In this section the learnings from that process are presented as visualisations as a contribution to the Body of Knowledge. The intention of this section and Appendix B is to provide an uncomplicated guide for those undertaking similar recovery projects. The visualisations are preceded by a brief introduction in this section, with Appendix B expanding on the diagrams with explanatory text and observations from the author.

Initial Considerations

Before embarking on a digital recovery project it is important to consider the final objective, as this will influence the methodologies, tools, technologies and techniques to be used. Chapter 3 – Epistemology and Methodology examined these topics in detail. The issues its addresses can be grouped into 3 distinct strands, summarised below (Fig. 39).

Figure 39 - Epistemological and Methodological Considerations. (Source: Author)

The selection of tools is of paramount importance and some issues, such as metadata support and OAI protocol compliance are non-negotiable in the era of Open Access. The diagram below (Fig. 40) illustrates the many considerations involved.

Figure 40 - Tool Selection Considerations for Digital Outputs. (Source: Author)

Stages of Digital Resource Creation Project

The creation of a digital resource is a complex process and Chapter 4 – Design and Implementation examined the topic in detail, Chapter 5 – Findings and Analysis described the challenges faced as the digital artefact was being developed and offered observations and solutions. The diagram below (Fig. 41) synthesises the design steps and the findings by illustrating the major tasks and objectives of each stage as a sequential workflow at each level.

Figure 41 - Stages of Digital Resource Creation Process. (Source: Author)

Dissemination and Preservation Options

The final stage of the workflow took as its focus the dissemination and preservation of the digital resource.

Figure 42 - Dissemination and Preservation Options for Digital Outputs. (Source: Author)

As stated above, this section has provided visualisations as a summary of the digital artefact creation process. Further detail is provided in the relevant chapters 3, 4 and 5, and as Appendix B – Guidelines for Similar Projects. In this way Appendix B is intended to be useful as a standalone guide for those undertaking similar recovery projects.

6.4 Limitations

A significant limitation to this research was the lack of literature relating to the issue of sustainability for digital projects in the Humanities. As an emerging paradigm, little in the way of rigorous academic research has been undertaken on the topic. In particular there was an absence

of literature examining how similar ‘lost’ legacy projects could be returned to the digital domain, and while this gap offered an opportunity to propose the research problem, the absence of any documented best practice or guidelines also provided a challenge.

While the literature review referenced the epistemological issues surrounding the term ‘digital humanities’ briefly (Pannacker, 2011; Piotrowski, 2018; Gold and Klein, 2019; McGinnis 2019) this dissertation did not seek to add to the debate, choosing instead to use and understand the term in the context of digital projects across all Humanities disciplines.

While the case study element of dissertation dealt with issues of methodologies, tools and techniques for research and dissemination, it did not seek to address the existential crisis that the Academy is currently facing due in no small part to the technology-enabled locus shift of knowledge production (Martinelli, 2016; Sörlin, 2018; Lee, 2021; Liu *et al.*, 2022). Nor did it examine issues arising from the changing landscape in scholarly publishing brought about by digital publication, such as: how success is quantified, and impact measured; changes to the business model of publishers; issues of ownership and intellectual rights (Terras, 2012; Schreibman, 2013; Simanowski, 2016).

The self-imposed design decision to use tools and technologies that provided low barriers to access in terms of technical expertise and financial outlay reduced the options for data management, CMS selection and hosting. The decision to operate within the parameters of Open Access, adhering to FAIR principles and Open Data guidelines, and using Open Source platforms and software also imposed limitations for the creation of the digital artefact.

Due to the limitation of time the digital artefact contains only a subset of the data that was available. While all available biographical information for writers associated with county Tipperary was included the bibliographic information which was available in the original dataset was intentionally omitted. Extracting this data posed a significant challenge due to constraints of time.

As noted by Drucker and Svenson ‘critical reflections on data structures and ideologies that are developed in information studies rarely find their way into the humanities’ (2016, p.11) and this dissertation has neither addressed any of the critical or intellectual constraints of the Omeka CMS nor considered how such platforms might ‘frame arguments...[and]...define and delimit what can be said through the structuring principles of its design’ (Ibid., p.18).

6.5 Future Work and Research

This dissertation addressed the challenge of sustainability for digital projects in the Humanities in Ireland. During the research process a number of areas meriting further exploration were identified by the author.

Future Work

The digital artefact delivered was a successful proof-of-concept and given appropriate time and funding it could be developed further.

Enhance current proof-of-concept

- Identify method to extract bibliographic information and append to existing Omeka entries
- Engage in additional research to fact-check entries and confirm key biographical attributes such as dates of birth/death, birthplace, places of association
- Provide links to external information sources, such as DIB or authors’ websites
- Provide DOI information for bibliographic items and links for Open Access versions
- Provide images for entries

Expand to include entire dataset

The data cleansing process was time-consuming, but lessons learned from the proof-of-concept process and further refinement (including identifying a technique for extracting bibliographic information) should allow for the expansion of the existing resource to include all c. 560 entries from the Munster Women Writers database.

Enhance expanded resource

The resource could be enhanced by further primary research to:

- Update bibliographic details for post-2000 publications for existing writers
- Include writers born or published post-2000

Further dissemination of original dataset

Prepare a version of the original dataset for deposit in Zenodo, DRI, Wikidata and OpenAccess repositories. This effort would include the dataset and documentation outlining the process undertaken to refine and revise it for deposit. The output of this is likely to be a .csv file accompanied by explanatory documents, including a data dictionary, in .pdf format.

Wikimedia Platform

Consideration should be given to the potential role of Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons and WikiData in making the MWW data more widely available. Although time-consuming, and not dynamic, there is a considerable amount to be gained from the visibility and accessibility that the platform provides. The Women in Red project was established in 2014 with the goal of ‘reducing systemic bias in the wiki movement’ (*Wikipedia:WikiProject Women in Red*, 2022). However, as of 15 August 2022 only 19.31% of English Wikipedia’s biographies were about women (Ibid.). This could be undertaken as an individual endeavour or might also suit as a workshop-style event. And as noted by McClenaghan (2020), it is possible to link datasets in Wikidata with the Wikipedia entries, which in turn could be linked to images, audio and video via Wikimedia Commons.

Future Peer Support Projects

Digital Citizenship in academia

Building on the learnings from the creation of the digital artefact and mindful of gaps identified by the review of the Irish digital landscape the following resources could be developed.

- Module for undergraduate students introducing them to sustainability issues for digital research output
- Module for post-graduate Humanities students to raise awareness of access, dissemination, and preservation topics, introduced as part of Research Methods
- Workshops for existing Humanities scholars introducing them to data management skills and raising awareness of lifecycle issues affecting the digital production of knowledge
- Encourage inclusion of Digital Manifest as per Shirazi and Zweibel (2020) with all academic submissions

Further Research

History of the Women in Irish Society Project (WISP)

As one of the first Humanities projects in Ireland to embrace an interdisciplinary approach, and one of the first to receive funding for digital resources (via PRTL11) WISP was a significant point in the development of the digital humanities in Ireland. A history of the project, and the many women it inspired, would represent an important addition to the literature.

A review of the *munsterwomen.ie* website project

This dissertation took as its case study the *munsterwomen.ie* website, but it did not seek to explore the reasons why it became a ‘lost’ digital project. An examination of the Munster Women Writers project structure, its use of technology and the events that led to the project’s disappearance from the web could provide learning for future scholars.

MWW as a feminist project

In her introduction to the print version O’Toole (2005) described the dictionary ‘as a feminist recovery project’ and the contextualisation of *munsterwomen.ie* as a feminist project rather than a database project is an important one. Groups marginalised by the Academy, such as women, do not historically attract much funding, meaning that their output, digital or otherwise, is more likely to be ‘lost’. While undertaking research for this dissertation parallels were found in a number of areas, not least a contemporaneous Cork-based project the Knitting Map (Gilson, 2012), a flagship project for the 2005 City of Culture. An investigation of the constructions of value, using these two projects to illustrate the perceived value of women’s output could, I suggest, provide much food for thought.

6.6 Conclusion

This dissertation proposed the research problem as the sustainability challenge that currently exists for digital projects in the Humanities in Ireland. It addressed the problem in two ways: intellectually, by identifying the key challenges and contextualising them within the structure and composition of the Irish landscape, and practically by taking a previously inaccessible resource and returning it to the digital domain. It has demonstrated what is possible using the tools and technologies of 2022, to facilitate access to the valuable output of the Irish Humanities.

The publicly funded research produced by Irish scholars is world class and the Academy needs to retain, and be seen to retain, its intellectual ownership. As publishing models shift and Open Access drives changes across the research ecosystem scholarship can easily become lost and diluted, being seen merely as data to be harvested, and exploited, by third parties. Irish research output should be viewed as a national resource, and ring-fenced as such, not by making it any less accessible or available, but by clearly situating it within the Irish domain, presented to the world via a national digital repository.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Digital Landscape for Humanities in Ireland, 2022 is divided into four parts:

A1 and A2 provide diagrams illustrating aspects of the digital landscape for the Humanities in Ireland

A3 Provides a summary of infrastructures in table form

A4 Provides an alphabetical list of all entities listed in A1, A2, and A3. The purpose of the list is to provide a brief description of each entity, the descriptions are taken verbatim from the referenced websites and no critical assessment has been made by the author.

Appendix B

Practical suggestions and advice for those undertaking similar legacy digital recovery projects.

Appendix C

A data dictionary intended to accompany the original MWW dataset, to aid understanding of field names and data types.

Appendix D

Details the data-mapping exercise undertaken to transfer information from the master Tipperary writers spreadsheet to the Omeka data model.

Appendix E

Provides further technical information about the customised installation of Omeka v3.0.2 for the creation of my digital artefact.

Appendix F

Copy of email confirming the digital artefact as OAI compliant.

Appendix A1 – Digital Landscape for Humanities in Ireland, August 2022

The digital landscape of the Humanities in Ireland in 2022 is a complex one. There is no central digital repository, national oversight body or dedicated infrastructure for the digital output from Humanities projects. Local silos, primarily third level institutions, enable access to content via their own repositories, DH departments or Digital Libraries. Many have links to EU organisations and some are members of national bodies such as DRI. The diagram below (Fig. 43) illustrates the links between institutions, DH bodies, funders and other organisations. The resource can be explored in more depth by using the [Interactive Version](#) (this link will bring you to the external website where the resource is hosted).

Link to Interactive Version on Mind Meister website:

<https://mm.tt/map/2345445780?t=AWrTwhN1ts>

This page has been archived at:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20220811151149/https://www.mindmeister.com/map/2345445780?t=AWrTwhN1ts>

Figure 43 - Digital Landscape of the Humanities in Ireland, August 2022 (Source: Author)

Appendix A2 - Third Level Repositories and Open Access, August 2022

The diagram below illustrates the links between Irish Third Level Institutions and Open Access aggregators and directories (Fig. 44). The resource can be explored in more depth by using the [interactive version](#) (this link will bring you to the external website where the resource is hosted).

Link to Interactive Version on Mind Meister website:

<https://www.mindmeister.com/map/2348879434>

Figure 44 - Open Access in Irish Third Level Institutions, August 2022 (Source: Author)

Appendix A3 - Third Level Repositories and Infrastructures

Legend

TLI:	Name of Third Level Institution
DL:	Digital Library
IR:	Institutional Repository:
DH Centre:	Centre or department focussed on digital humanities outputs
DRI:	Member of Digital Repository of Ireland
Other:	Additional repositories hosted by the TLI
Platform:	Software platform on which repository runs
CORE:	Contents aggregated by CORE (OAI harvest)
BASE:	Contents aggregated by BASE (OAI harvest)

Table 5 - Summary of Third Level Repositories and Infrastructures

TLI	DL	IR	DH Centre	DRI	Other	Platform	CORE	BASE
DCU	Yes	DORAS	No	Member		EPrints3	Yes	Yes
Maynooth	Yes	MURALS	Arts & Humanities Institute	Member & Manager	AIRO; IQDA	EPrints3	No	Yes
NCAD	No	NIVAL	No	Member		?hosted by UCD?	No	No
NUIG	Yes	ARAN	Moore Institute	Member & Manager		DSpace	Yes	Yes
RIA*	No	No		Member & Manager	DRI*	Fedora	N/a	N/a
TCD	Yes	TARA	Trinity Centre for Digital Humanities	Member & Manager		DSpace	No	Yes
UCC	Yes	CORA	Dept of DAH	Member		DSpace	Yes	Yes
UCD	Yes	Research Repository UCD	Humanities Institute; Centre for Cultural Analytics	No	ISSDA; NIVAL ?	Fedora (DigLib) DSpace (ResearchRep)	Yes	Yes
UL	Yes	ULIR	No	No		DSpace	Yes	Yes

Source: Author, with software data from OpenDOAR

https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/view/repository_by_country/Ireland.html

Appendix A4 – Short Description of Entities Referenced in Appendices A1-3

The purpose of the list below is to provide a brief description of each entity referenced in the preceding diagrams (Fig. 43 and Fig. 44) the descriptions are taken *verbatim* from the referenced websites and no critical assessment has been made by the author in this section. For contextual critiques of many of the organisations listed see Chapter 2 Literature Review, and Chapter 6 Conclusion.

ALLEA ([link](#))

ALLEA is the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, representing more than 50 academies from about 40 EU and non-EU countries. Since its foundation in 1994, ALLEA speaks out on behalf of its members on the European and international stages, promotes science as a global public good, and facilitates scientific collaboration across borders and disciplines.

AODHO ([link](#))

The Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (ADHO) promotes and supports digital research and teaching across all arts and humanities disciplines, acting as a community-based advisory force, and supporting excellence in research, publication, collaboration and training.

CESSDA ([link](#))

CESSDA provides large-scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences. It brings together social science data archives across Europe, with the aim of promoting the results of social science research and supporting national and international research and cooperation. The CESSDA Consortium is currently composed of 22 member countries and one observer. Several European countries are in the process of becoming a CESSDA member or observer. CESSDA also has partners in a number of countries outside of the consortium.

CLS INFRA

The European Commission-funded CLS INFRA project will help to build the shared and sustainable infrastructure needed to undertake literary studies in the digital age.

CONUL ([link](#))

The Consortium of National and University Libraries (CONUL) is the representative body of research libraries in Ireland and Northern Ireland. Its members are: Dublin City University, Maynooth University, National Library of Ireland, National University of Ireland, Galway, Queen's University Belfast, RCSI, University of Medicine and Health Sciences, Royal Irish Academy, Technological University Dublin, Trinity College Dublin, University College Cork, University College Dublin, University of Limerick, Ulster University.

CoreTrustSeal ([link](#))

CoreTrustSeal is an international, community based, non-governmental, and non-profit organization promoting sustainable and trustworthy data infrastructures. CoreTrustSeal offers to any interested data repository a core level certification based on the DSA–WDS Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements catalogue and procedures. This universal catalogue of requirements reflects the core characteristics of trustworthy data repositories and is the culmination of a cooperative effort between DSA and WDS under the umbrella of the Research Data Alliance to merge their data repositories certifications.

COST ([link](#))

The European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) is a funding organisation for the creation of research networks, called COST Actions. These networks offer an open space for collaboration among scientists across Europe (and beyond) and thereby give impetus to research advancements and innovation.

DARIAH-EU ([link](#))

The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) aims to enhance and support digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. DARIAH is a network of people, expertise, information, knowledge, content, methods, tools and technologies from its member countries. It develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure in support of ICT-based research practices and sustains researchers in using them to build, analyse and interpret digital resources.

DFHERIS ([link](#))

The Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science funds and creates policy for the higher and further education and research sectors. We also oversee the work of the state agencies and public institutions operating in these areas.

DRI ([link](#))

As a national infrastructure for the arts, social sciences, and humanities, DRI provides reliable, long-term, sustained access to social and cultural digital data. We make this data openly available in line with the FAIR data principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. Our aim is to safeguard Ireland’s social, cultural, and historical record through active management of digital content over time to ensure that this content remains accessible to researchers, cultural heritage enthusiasts, and members of the public into the future. We support best practice in digital archiving, digital preservation, Open Access, Open Research, and FAIR data sharing.

EADH ([link](#))

The EADH brings together and represents the Digital Humanities in Europe across the entire spectrum of disciplines that research, develop, and apply digital humanities methods and technology. These include art history, cultural studies, history, image processing, language and literature studies, manuscripts studies, and musicology, amongst

others. The EADH also supports the formation of DH interest groups in Europe that are defined by region, language, methodological focus or other criteria.

E-Humanities Working Group [\(link\)](#)

The Working Group E-Humanities identifies and raises awareness for priorities and concerns of the digital humanities, contributes to the Open Science and Open Access agenda from a humanities and social sciences perspective, and builds consensus on common standards and best practices in e-humanities scholarship and digitisation.

Enterprise Ireland [\(link\)](#)

COST is an intergovernmental framework, for European Cooperation in Science and Technology, allowing the coordination of nationally-funded research on a European level. Enterprise Ireland manages Ireland's national membership of COST. The goal of COST is to ensure that Europe holds a strong position in the field of scientific and technical research for peaceful purposes, by increasing European cooperation and interaction in this field. This research initiative makes it possible for the various national facilities, institutes, universities and private industry to work jointly on a wide range of Research and Development (R&D) activities.

EOSC [\(link\)](#)

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is an environment for hosting and processing research data to support EU science. The ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to provide European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes.

ESFRI [\(link\)](#)

Irish rep is from Science Foundation Ireland (SFI). ESFRI, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, is a strategic instrument to develop the scientific integration of Europe and to strengthen its international outreach. The competitive and open access to high quality Research Infrastructures supports and benchmarks the quality of the activities of European scientists, and attracts the best researchers from around the world.

Europeana [\(link\)](#)

Europeana provides cultural heritage enthusiasts, professionals, teachers, and researchers with digital access to European cultural heritage material. Why? To inspire and inform fresh perspectives and open conversations about our history and culture. To share and enjoy our rich cultural heritage. To use it to create new things.

HEA [\(link\)](#)

The HEA has a statutory responsibility, at central government level, for the effective governance and regulation of higher education institutions and the higher education system.

IHA ([link](#))

In September 2013 the Irish Humanities Alliance (IHA) was established as a joint initiative of humanities researchers within 11 higher education and research institutions including all the universities across the island of Ireland and the Royal Irish Academy (RIA) which hosts and supports the IHA.

IRC ([link](#))

The mission of the Irish Research Council is to support excellence in research talent, knowledge and engagement. Our Strategic Plan 2020-2024 sets out how we will achieve this over the next five years.

National Archives ([link](#))

The records of Government Departments and their agencies are transferred to the National Archives when they are 30 years old. Collection Care and Public Services Division is comprised of a number of divisions, including Public Services, Archive Repository and Digital Management and Conservation Services

National Library of Ireland ([link](#))

The National Library will collect, preserve, promote and make accessible the documentary and intellectual record of the life of Ireland and contribute to the provision of access to the larger universe of recorded knowledge.

NORF ([link](#))

The National Open Research Forum provides a space for communication, consultation and cooperation among key stakeholders in the research system regarding strategic issues and overarching policies and procedures on open research. The Forum combines the expertise of representatives from policy, research funding, research performing, the library sector, enterprise and other key stakeholders in the research system from across Ireland.

SFI ([link](#))

Science Foundation Ireland funds research in the areas of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) which promotes and assists the development and competitiveness of industry, enterprise and employment in Ireland.

RDA ([link](#))

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 by the European Commission, the United States Government's National Science Foundation and National Institute of Standards and Technology, and the Australian Government's Department of Innovation with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data.

re3data ([link](#))

Research data are valuable and ubiquitous. Permanent access to research data is a challenge for all stakeholders in the scientific community. Long-term preservation and the principle of open access to research data offer broad opportunities for the scientific community. In the last decade, more and more universities and research centres

established research data repositories allowing permanent access to data sets in a trustworthy environment. Due to disciplinary requirements, the landscape of data repositories is very heterogeneous. Thus, it is difficult for researchers, funding bodies, publishers, and scholarly institutions to select appropriate repositories for storing and searching research data.

UK-IRL Digital Humanities Network ([link](#))

Seeking to nurture the capacity for excellent research and teaching in DH, to establish and sustain more effective connections with non-HE sectors (notably Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums), and to create new pathways for collaboration, this project will undertake research and consultation vital to the implementation of a permanent Digital Humanities association within the UK and Ireland

Third Level Repositories and Digital Humanities Centres

Note: Unless otherwise stated all third level organisations are clients of HEAnet and members of DRI, CONUL, IHA

*= not member of DRI **=not member of CONUL or IHA

Dublin City University

DORAS ([link](#))

DCU Online Research Access Service

National College of Art and Design**

NIVAL ([link](#))

The National Irish Visual Arts Library (NIVAL) is a public research resource dedicated to the documentation of 20th and 21st century Irish visual art and design. NIVAL collects, stores and makes accessible for research an unparalleled collection of documentation about Irish art in all media.

National University of Ireland, Galway

NUIG Moore Institute ([link](#))

The Moore Institute hosts a large variety of digital humanities projects and resources, and offers training and support for students and scholars engaged in digital humanities research.

NUIG Digital Library ([link](#))

The library has an exciting collection of services in the Digital Scholarship area - the use of digital evidence, new methods of inquiry, research, publication, and preservation.

ARAN ([link](#))

Access to Research at NUI Galway (ARAN) is the Institutional Repository for NUI Galway and encourages open access of NUI Galway research outputs.

National University of Ireland, Maynooth

MU Digital Library (link)

The Library has a growing collection of digitised, born digital and electronic resources. In conjunction with various partners, the Library has begun a programme to digitise material from its collections. It has a large collection of databases, e-journals and e-books both sourced and maintained locally and through the IReL initiative.

AIRO (link)

The All-Island Research Observatory (AIRO) undertakes academic and applied mapping research and produces spatial datasets and specialist tools to aid in their analysis. Based at Maynooth University, AIRO is the leading spatial analysis and planning unit within the National Institute for Regional and Spatial Analysis (NIRSA).

Arts & Humanities Institute (link)

The Institute houses a number of funded research projects and supports the incubation of new research projects led by Institute members.

IQDA (link)

The Irish Qualitative Data Archive (IQDA) is a central access point for qualitative social science data generated in or about Ireland. The archive frames the parameters and standards for archiving qualitative data within the Irish research community.

MURAL (link)

Institutional repository.

Royal Irish Academy (link)

The Digital Repository of Ireland is housed by the RIA but is not its digital repository.

Trinity College, Dublin

TARA (link)

TARA is an open access repository, which means that the full text of the work deposited here is freely accessible to the world via the web.

Trinity Centre for Digital Humanities (link)

Founded in 2006, the Trinity Long Room Hub Arts and Humanities Research Institute is dedicated to advancing Trinity College Dublin's rich tradition of research excellence in the Arts and Humanities, on an individual, collaborative and inter-disciplinary basis

Virtual Trinity Library (link)

Virtual Trinity Library is opening up the unique and distinct collections of the Library of Trinity College Dublin, catalysing research and safeguarding the iconic treasures of the Library of Trinity College Dublin for generations to come. This ambitious, multi-year initiative is to catalogue, conserve, digitise and research these unique collections of national importance making them accessible to a global audience, from schoolchildren to scholars.

University College, Cork

CORA (link)

CORA is University College Cork's online, open access institutional repository, established by UCC Library to collect, store and disseminate the digital research output of the UCC scholarly community. CORA gives you free open access to University College Cork's scholarly and scientific research publications and theses. [Text-based content only]

University College, Dublin*

UCD Digital Library (link)

UCD Digital Library refers to the digital collections and online services made available by the Library of University College Dublin. It is an archive comprising an organisation, namely, the UCD Library and particularly its Research Services and Information Technology Services divisions, and technical systems, namely, the UCD Digital Repository and its services framework. It is a curated, preservation-oriented resource that seeks to comply to internationally endorsed best practices and standards for an OAIS-compliant Trusted Digital Repository.

Research Repository UCD (link)

Research Repository UCD is a digital collection of open access scholarly research publications from University College Dublin. Research Repository UCD collects, preserves and makes freely available publications including peer-reviewed articles, working papers and conference papers created by UCD researchers. Where material has already been published it is made available subject to the open-access policies of the original publishers. This service is maintained by UCD Library.

UCD Humanities Institute (link)

UCD Humanities Institute seeks to explore the emerging synergy between traditional humanities interpretative skills and qualitative techniques with the quantitative potential inherent in the new digital archives at our disposal which can open up very long term historical perspectives and multiplicities of cultures, languages and communities for analysis.

Centre for Cultural Analytics (link)

The UCD Centre for Cultural Analytics provides a coherent research ecosystem for the digital humanities, develops support for ongoing collaboration, acts as a focus and host for international networks and an incubator for new projects in a rapidly developing and prestigious field.

University of Limerick*

UL Digital Library (link)

The University of Limerick Digital Library is a free, online repository of digital cultural heritage material hosted by the University of Limerick.

ULIR (link)

Institutional Repository. The new digital repository is currently in beta testing. *This repository is about to be relaunched, Q3/4 2022*

MIRR (link)

Here you can access the digital archive collections, and published and unpublished works of faculty and researchers at Mary Immaculate College.

Appendix B - Guidelines for Similar Recovery Projects

The purpose of this appendix is to offer advice and guidance to others engaged in the process of returning a legacy project to the digital domain. The recommendations are equally applicable to those embarking on research which will result in the creation of new digital resources. All recommendations are informed directly by the experiences of the author when creating the digital artefact for this dissertation.

Note that this appendix includes the same visualisations as provided in Section 6.3.2.

Considerations of epistemology and methodology

Figure 39 - Epistemological and Methodological Considerations. (Source: Author)

- Collect datasets, ancillary documents, if possible speak to members of the original project team
- Decide on the purpose of the project, it could be to: (Re)distribute the data, (Re)create a resource for the historical record or (Re)present the data in a new way or to a new audience
- The purpose directly impacts the methodology that you will use. You could choose from, or combine, any of the following: Redistribution, Repurposing, Restoration or Emulation
- Consider how you wish to present the data and let the purpose of your recovery project dictate the tool you select, rather than allowing the tool you select dictate how your data can be represented. Your options could include: a decision not to interpret the data and simply present it as is; a repackaging of the dataset in a different format; some level of

interpretation using knowledge representation tools such as maps and timelines; or as an enhanced dataset - using encoding or Linked Open Data structures to add value.

Figure 40 - Tool Selection Considerations for Digital Outputs. (Source: Author)

Standards, Open and FAIR

Regardless of the manner in which your data is presented always ensure that the tools and technologies adhere to the FAIR Principles and Open Access requirements. This is no longer a negotiable requirement for research outputs. It is now a requirement of all public research funding. Ensuring that your digital resource is OAI compliant means that it can be ‘seen’ by other research repositories and data aggregators, without any human intervention, something that is facilitated by the structured metadata and associated protocols.

Further information on FAIR can be found at: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Further information on OAI can be found at: <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

Metadata

Metadata is not as complicated as it sounds. Often described as ‘data about data’, it is simply descriptive information about an object - examples of metadata for a book might include the title, the date and place of publication and the author name.

A **metadata standard** is an agreed set of such terms, which allows for different objects to be described in a similar way. There are many different metadata standards but one of the simplest, most flexible and most commonly used is called Dublin Core. It has only 15 core terms, and you don’t need to use them all when describing an object. Every librarian in your organisation will understand what metadata is, and they are more often than not happy to explain how to use it.

More detailed information about Dublin Core can be found at: <https://www.dublincore.org/>

Process Steps

Figure 41 - Stages of Digital Resource Creation Process. (Source: Author)

Begin by making a project lifecycle plan

Involve all stakeholders from the beginning. Ensure meaningful engagement and agree a shared vision. Then write it down. Decide who is responsible for the different aspects of the project and ensure buy-in from the beginning. Consider what support the digital resource might require after the project ends. Create a data management plan and identify stewardship requirements. There are many organisations offering free tools and templates for the creation of both project and data management plans.

For examples see the Digital Curation Centre at:

<https://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans/guidance-examples>

King's Digital Lab has a GitHub resource containing many useful templates. It can be accessed at:

<https://github.com/kingsdigitallab/sdlc-for-rse/wiki>.

Start small

Always start with a small pilot dataset. Make this only as large as required to cover the main variants in your legacy dataset. The time spent finessing protocols and mappings at this stage will be repaid many times over.

Document design decisions

If you're taking a pre-existing dataset and changing its format or structure, whether by adding or removing content, document the process and the reasons behind it. A simple list of design decisions is invaluable to anyone building on your work.

Create a data dictionary

Create a simple document that explains all of the terms you use with your dataset. Analogous to a glossary, consider that people reviewing your material 20 years hence may not fully appreciate what you meant by 'author_role_affiliate', provide a brief explanation and an example for each term.

Create a project summary document

Use simple terms to provide an explanatory document to accompany your resource. Detail the scope and limitations of your resource, describe the methodologies, tools and standards that you have used. Include a reference to an archived version of the resource. Provide contact details for project members.

Dissemination and Preservation

Avoid broken links

Of the twelve digital resources listed on the munsterwomen.ie website in 2013 only two remain valid URLs. To avoid this happening to your digital resource create an archived version at the end of your project and use this link when referencing your own work. Link to this and not to the live site once it ceases to be maintained. Do this using the Internet Archive's free Wayback Machine which can be found at: <https://archive.org/web/web.php>

Create a DOI

For all digital outputs consider assigning a DOI. A Digital Object Identifier is a unique reference number, issued as an ISO standard, for digital objects. Their creation is controlled and managed on a not-for-profit basis by a number of registered agencies. **Zenodo** creates a DOI automatically upon deposit of material in their repository, and offers DOI versioning, allowing you to edit/update files after a DOI has been assigned.

Options for Dissemination and Preservation (Fig. 42)

- **Zenodo** is an offering of the EU Open Science initiative operated by CERN and OpenAIRE - uploaded research is given a DOI and stored by CERN, an organisation with long-standing funding support. It also offer GitHub integration. It accepts all file types, and all research outputs. Content can be made publicly accessible, remain hidden, or be restricted to specific groups. There are no costs associated with depositing material in Zenodo. More information can be found at: <https://zenodo.org/>
- The **Internet Archive** is a non-profit digital library. Use the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine to create a digital snapshot of your website. This doesn't require a user account. You can also create a free account and upload content which you have the right to share. It accepts all file types, and all research outputs. All content is publicly accessible. There are no costs associated with depositing material in the Internet Archive. More information can be found at: <https://archive.org/>
- **Wikimedia** is a non-profit foundation, it provides a number of tools and platforms to make data widely available and freely accessible. It is community-driven project, which allows

anyone to upload and edit information, for that reason is not often considered as an appropriate method of scholarly dissemination. However its ubiquitous nature, and user friendly platform, more than compensate for its occasionally unreliable information, and should not allow it to be overlooked as a useful means to communicate information to the wider public.

More information can be found at: <https://www.wikimedia.org/>

- **GitHub** has traditionally been associated with software projects, however it is at its core a digital repository which accepts all file types, and all research outputs. Users can create wikis and provide all manner of explanatory documentation. The content can be confined to specified user(s), or made publicly accessible. GitHub integrates with Zenodo. There are no costs associated with creating your own GitHub repository or depositing content.

More information can be found at: <https://github.com/>

Figure 42 - Dissemination and Preservation Options for Digital Outputs. (Source: Author)

An additional note on Irish websites

The National Library of Ireland is not currently supported in its collection of digital-born content by legislation (or funding) and there is no .ie domain crawl. Contact the NLI and request that they harvest your site to the Irish Domain Web Archive which they manage. More information can be found at: <https://www.nli.ie/en/irish-domain-web-archive.aspx> or by contacting webarchives@nli.ie.

Appendix C – Munster Women Writers Data Dictionary

This appendix is a data dictionary intended to accompany the original MWW dataset in order to aid understanding of field names and data types. The interpretations have been informed by discussion with some original project members and reference to the Dictionary of Munster Women Writers, 1800-2000 (O’Toole, 2005), the print volume that was published in tandem with the *munsterwomen.ie* online resource.

Legend

- ID:** Numerical reference number to aid identification of each field
- Field Name:** Name which appears as a header for each column the dataset
- Description:** My understanding of the intended content type for each field
- Entries:** Number of fields populated with values for each. Maximum value =3917
- Sample Text:** Extracted text from fields
- Notes:** Additional information on field values, using personal interpretation of author

Table 6 - MWW Data Dictionary

ID	Field Name	Description	Entries	Sample text	Notes
1	id	Database row id	3917	4	
2	procite_id	Reference ID from legacy database that original data was stored in	3917	12770	Removed
3	Extent_Of_Work	Dates associated with the writer	530	1896-1982	Inconsistent in terms of specificity, includes entries b-d, b only, d only; fl. (the years in which the writer was popular); Contemporary, and null
4	Author_Analytic	Name of writer if work not a monograph	1679	Barrington, Margaret	
5	Author_Role1	Role of writer in publication	251	Editor; trans.	
6	Author_Affiliation	Name of co-author	171	and John Barrett	
7	Title_Analytic	Title of work, when published in a longer work	1006	Rev. of We are Besieged	
8	Medium_Designator1	Genre for individual work	2801	Essay	

9	Connective_Phrase1	Unclear	108	:	Field contains punctuation mostly.
10	Author_Monographic	Writer of a work	2495	Barrington, Margaret	
11	Author_Role2	Role of another writer associated with the work	434	Eds.	
12	Title_Monographic	Title of work, when not published in another work	2554	The Rebel's Wife	
13	Journal_Title	Publication in which a work is published	672	The Bell	
14	Journal_Title_Without_The	cf13	672	Bell	
15	Journal_Title_Without_An	cf13	672		
16	Title	Used for EN translation of GA titles	59	Old John	
17	Reprint_Status	Unused	0		
18	Place_Of_Meeting	Unclear	91	Dublin	Always corresponds with place of publication
19	Medium_Designator2	Language of publication	3842	E	E for English, G for Irish. Values include E; G; E/G; G/E.
20	Edition	Used only when indicating secondary source	70	Secondary Sources	
21	Author_Subsiary	Name of translator	92	Roberto Samesi	
22	Author_Role3	cf21 Role of another writer	53	trans	Links with Author_Subsiary
23	Place_Of_Publication	Place of publication	2451	London	
24	Publisher_Name	Name of publisher	2469	Hutchinson	
25	Date_Of_Publication	Date of publication	2889	1979	
26	Date_Of_Copyright	Date of copyright	503	1979	
27	Volume_ID	Journal - Volume number	560	7	
28	Report_ID	Used for alternate or associated publisher name	110	Coward McCann & Geoghegan	
29	Issue_ID	Journal - Issue number	304	2	
30	Location_In_Work	Journal - Page numbers	687	132-39	Inconsistent formatting. Examples: 132-139; 132-39; 01-Mar
31	Packaging_Method	Unclear	3905	P	All fields contain value P or R. Possibly R indicates republished ?

32	Place_Of_Birth	Place of birth of the writer	411	West Cork.	Inconsistent in terms of specificity, ranges from county to parish.
33	Place_Of_Association	Place of association of the writer	507	Clonmel	Can contain multiple placenames; inconsistent in terms of specificity, ranges from county to parish.
34	Series_Editor	Name of series editor	9	Raymond Gillespie	
35	Series_Editor_Role	Unclear	2		
36	Series_Title	Title of series which the work is part of	41	Bright Sparks	
37	Series_Volume_ID	Series volume number	23	17	Inconsistent formatting, contains both numbers and roman numerals
38	Series_Issue_ID	Series issue number	0	n/a	
39	Document_Type	Month of publication	43	Jan	Links with Volume_ID
40	Connective_Phrase2	All genres associated with writer	542	Novels, Short Stories, Poetry	Links with Notes field. Contains multiple values separated by commas, all genres assoc with writer.
41	Availability	Unclear	3	[UCD] GEN 891.628MHI	Inconsistent content: Some call numbers
42	Location_URL	Unclear	12	NLI Collection List no. 56. Mss. 35.683-699	Inconsistent content: Some URLs, call numbers
43	CODEN	Unclear	8	see 'IOTA'	Inconsistent content: Cross reference field ?
44	ISSN	Unused - International Standard Book Number	0	n/a	
45	ISBN	International Standard Book Number	4	950600806	Not used - only 4 entries
46	Notes	Biographical Summary	560		Free text, varying levels of detail
47	Abstract	Descriptive field	126	Illustrated by Alfred Kerr	Infrequently populated. Used primarily to indicate illustrator information
48	Call_Number	Unused	0	n/a	
49	Keywords	Name of writer	3917	Barrington, Margaret	This was the key field in the dataset. The only place linking all bibliographical entries with writer.

Appendix D - Omeka Mapping

This appendix details the data-mapping exercise undertaken to transfer information from the master Tipperary writers spreadsheet to the Omeka data model.

Legend

Field Name: Name which appears as a header for each column the dataset

Item Type: Element sets containing default values within Omeka

Source: Auto-mapped: Brought in from source spreadsheet using CSV Import plugin

Auto on item creation: Fields pre-populated using Default Dublin Core plugin

Add post-ingest: Value manually added post-ingest

Mapped (edit pre-ingest): Created additional field pre-ingest and then mapped using CSV Import plugin

Value: Example of text in the field

Maps/Input: Field from original dataset that Omeka is mapped against

Description: Intended content type for each field

Table 7 - Omeka Import Data Mapping

Field Name	Item	Source	Value	Maps/Input	Description
Title	Default DC	Auto Mapped -	Lane, Temple	49: Keywords	A name given to the resource
Subject	Default DC	Auto Mapped -	Lane, Temple	49: Keywords	The topic of the resource
Description	Default DC	Auto on item creation	Bibliographic Dictionary Entry	None	An account of the resource
Creator	Default DC	Auto on item creation	Tina O'Toole	None	An entity primarily responsible for making the resource
Source	Default DC	Auto on item creation	Munster Writers University Cork Women Project, College	None	A related resource from which the described resource is derived
Publisher	Default DC	Auto on item creation	Women in Irish Society University Cork Project, College	None	An entity responsible for making the resource available
Date	Default DC	Auto Mapped -	1899-1978	3: Extent_Of_Work	A point or period of time associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource

Contributor	Default DC	Add post-ingest	Two Irish Language editors	None	An entity responsible for making contributions to the resource
Rights	Default DC	Auto on item creation	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	None	Information about rights held in and over the resource
Relation	Default DC	Not used	Not used	None	A related resource from which the described resource is derived
Format	Default DC	Auto on item creation	Text	None	The file format, physical medium, or dimensions of the resource
Language	Default DC	Auto Mapped	EN or GA	None	A language of the resource
Type	Default DC	Auto on item creation	Bibliographic Dictionary Entry	None	The nature or genre of the resource
Identifier	Default DC	Not used	Not used	None	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context
Coverage	Default DC	Auto on item creation	Munster, Women, Writers, 1800-2000	None	The spatial or temporal topic of the resource, the spatial applicability of the resource, or the jurisdiction under which the resource is relevant
Birth Date	Person	Mapped (edit pre-ingest)	1899	3: Extent_Of_Work (splitDOB)	.
Death Date	Person	Mapped (edit pre-ingest)	1978	3: Extent_Of_Work (splitDOD)	.
Birth Place	Person	Auto Mapped	Dublin	32: Place_Of_Birth	.
Place of Association	Person - custom	Auto Mapped	Lismore, Waterford Co	33: Place_Of_Association	.
Biographical Text	Person	Auto Mapped	Lorem ipsen	46: Notes	.
Bibliography	Person	Add post-ingest	.	.	.
Writing Genre	Person - custom	Auto Mapped	Novels, Poetry	40: Connective_Phrase2	.
Logainm Permanent Link	Person - custom	Add post-ingest	https://www.logainm.ie/1416760.aspx	.	.

Appendix E - Omeka Technical and Plugins

This appendix provides further technical information about the customised installation of Omeka v3.0.2 for the creation of the digital artefact. It gives details on code changes, the installation and use of plugins, and the system specification.

Code Changes

Two situations (detailed below) arose whereby a line of code in the downloaded Omeka instance needed to be altered. As the files to be altered are system files it is important to enable 'Show Hidden Files' in preferences first and the process to alter the code can be undertaken using any basic text edit tool. For these code changes I accessed the application files via my service provider's File Manager tool (Fig. 47) downloading files to my desktop, I then made the appropriate changes using VisualCodeStudio, before uploading again.

Figure 45 - Reclaim Hosting File Manager Error Code Change. (Source: Author Screenshot)

Enable error messages

Omeka, by default, does not display descriptive error messages. This can cause frustration when trying to trouble-shoot. In advance of working with Omeka I enabled descriptive error messages by amending the `.htaccess` file using the steps outlined at the following link:

https://omeka.org/classic/docs/Troubleshooting/Retrieving_Error_Messages/

Set PHP path

Omeka requires the explicit setting of the PHP path in order for a number of plugins (including Neatline and CSV Import) to run. I discovered this after multiple attempts to run the CSV Import operation gave me errors. The support pages from my service provider gave me the solution which required an alteration to the application's *conFig.ini* file. The steps are outlined at:

<https://support.reclaimhosting.com/hc/en-us/articles/1500005620481#fixing-background-php-path-for-omeka-omeka-s-0-0>

Plugins

The following section lists all the plugins that I installed to the standard Omeka instance to enhance its core functionality, the process of adding the plugins was the same for each, requiring me to upload the specific folder to the application's own plugins folder. As the file management tool available via my service provider Reclaim Hosting did not allow for the direct uploading of folders, I used the free open source application FileZilla (*FileZilla*, n.d.) as the FTP client.

Bulk Metadata Editor

This plugin allows for global editing of records in the database.

Clickable Links Plus

This plugin enables the creation of clickable hyperlinks in plaintext fields. I applied this to the *Logainm* Permanent Link field and the Relation field.

COinS

This plugin allows for the embedding of bibliographic metadata in the html address of a item page, enabling the end-user to employ tools such as Zotero.

CSV Export Format

This allows end-users to export records as a .csv file. I used this to assess how the source metadata was mapping to DC.

CSV Import

Allows for the bulk ingest of items and associated metadata. I used this for the initial ingest of data from my MWW dataset once I had completed the initial data-mapping process.

Default Dublin Core

Allows for auto-population of DC fields. This greatly speeded-up the creation of records by assigning values to fields at point of record creation (either manual or via ingest).

Geolocation

The built-in geolocation tool adds location data (single location per item) directly to each item.

Neatline

Neatline offers a suite of tools to enhance the creation of exhibits, such as timeline and maps. As well as the main plugins there are ancillary widgets which provide additional functionality. At present the support and development of the toolset is ‘on hiatus while we seek a different institution to take over its future maintenance, development, and support.’ (Neatline, 2022), which is worrying for the Omeka community which relies on its tools. All of the following Neatline plugins were used for the creation of the map:

Neatline; Neatline Widget ~ SIMILE Timeline; Neatline Widget ~ Text;

Neatline Widget ~ Waypoints

Although I also installed the Neatline Features and Neatline Time plugins I was unable to get either to function correctly.

OAI-PMH Repository

Exposes Omeka items to repository harvesters using the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting, enabling visibility of the Dublin Core metadata to third parties also using the protocol.

OAI-PMH Harvester

I added this plugin to enable the functionality of OAI harvesting, although it is not something that I have implemented as part of this proof-of-concept project.

Simple Pages

This plugin facilitates the creation of basic web pages for the Omeka site, I used this to create the About pages.

System Configuration

A snapshot of the system configuration I used for digital artefact creation, including plugin versions (Fig. 48).

System Information	
User	
Browser	Mozilla/5.0 (Macintosh; Intel Mac OS X 10_15_7) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/103.0.0.0 Safari/537.36
Role	super
System	
Omeka	3.0.2
PHP	7.4.30 (cgi-fcgi)
OS	Linux 3.10.0 x86_64
MySQL Server	8.0.30
MySQL Client	mysqlnd 7.4.30
PHP Extensions	
Regular	bcmath, bz2, calendar, cgi-fcgi, Core, ctype, curl, date, dba, dom, enchant, exif, fileinfo, filter, ftp, gd, gettext, gmp, hash, iconv, imagick, imap, intl, ionCube Loader, json, ldap, libxml, mbstring, mysqli, mysqlnd, odbc, openssl, pcntl, pcre, PDO, pdo_mysql, PDO_ODBC, pdo_pgsql, pdo_sqlite, pgsql, Phar, posix, pspell, readline, Reflection, session, shmop, SimpleXML, snmp, soap, sockets, SPL, sqlite3, standard, sysvmsg, sysvsem, sysvshm, tidy, tokenizer, xml, xmlreader, xmlrpc, xmlwriter, xsl, Zend OPcache, zip, zlib
Zend	the ionCube PHP Loader + ionCube24, Zend OPcache
Plugins	
BulkMetadataEditor	2.4
ClickableLinksPlus	1.3.2
Coins	2.1
CsvExport	1.1.2
CsvImport	2.0.6
DefaultDC	1.0
ExhibitBuilder	3.5.3
Geolocation	3.2.2
Neatline	2.6.4
NeatlineFeatures	2.0.5
NeatlineSimile	2.0.4
NeatlineText	1.1.0
NeatlineTime	2.1.2
NeatlineWaypoints	2.0.2
OaiPmhRepository	2.2
OaipmhHarvester	2.0.3
SimplePages	3.2.1
Themes	
berlin	2.7.2
default	2.6.5
seasons	2.6.2 (current)

Figure 46 - Omeka System Configuration. (Source: Omeka Screenshot)

Appendix F - OAI Compliance

The Omeka resource is OAI compliant and has also been registered with the Open Archives Initiative as a repository.

 Apache
OAI Validation (step 2): <https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/oai-pmh-repository/request>
To: Joan Murphy

We received a request to register the following repository:

Base URL:
<https://munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com/oai-pmh-repository/request>
adminEmail: joan.murphy@gmail.com

Summary - *success*

- * Namespace declared for v2.0 oai-identifiers is munsterwomenwriters.joanofarchives.com
- * Uses https URIs (not specified in protocol)
- * Total tests passed: 40
- * Total warnings: 0
- * Total error count: 0
- * Validation status: COMPLIANT

Complete log available at
<http://www.openarchives.org/Register/ValidateSite?log=UVYJSWHY>

Your repository validated (at Protocol Version 2.0) according to our OAI-PMH validation service.

Your repository has been registered in the OAI database of conforming repositories.

Figure 47 - OAI Compliance email. (Source: Author Screenshot)